

Modelling of Coronal Mass Ejections Based on Data from the STEREO- and SOHO-Mission in Preparation for the Future Space Weather Mission Vigil

Abschlussarbeit im Rahmen der Prüfung
im Studiengang Physik (B.A.)
an der Universität Göttingen

vorgelegt am: 26.09.2022

von: Enno Müller

aus: Neubrandenburg

1. Gutachter: Dr. V. Bothmer
2. Gutachter: Prof. Dr. A. Reiners

Universität Göttingen
Institut für Astrophysik und Geophysik

Abstract

Coronal mass ejections (CMEs) are large-scale outburst of coronal plasma bound in flux rope-like magnetic structures accelerated into the heliosphere. They can trigger strong geomagnetic storms on Earth that pose serious threats to important foundations of our modern society, such as navigation and communication. Therefore, precise arrival predictions of CMEs are of great importance. Vigil is a new mission to the Lagrange point 5 (L5) in the Sun-Earth system in development at the European Space Agency (ESA). In an effort to investigate the expected improvements in CME arrival time predictions from L5 resulting from multi-viewpoint observations, this work analyses CME events selected in particular in preparation for the Vigil mission. These events are reconstructed using the Graduated Cylindrical Shell (GCS) modelling technique, providing a reference point for further analysis in preparation for the mission. In addition, a new propagation model, the Modified Drag-Based Model (MODBM), is introduced, which integrates more recent scientific findings into the well-known and well-studied Drag-Based Model (DBM). The necessary input parameters of both models for modelling the Earth-directed events are determined. Using both models, the arrival times of the Earth-directed CMEs are predicted. The results of the propagation modelling are compared to each other and to interplanetary coronal mass ejection (ICME) signatures identified in in-situ solar wind measurements, however, no statement is made about a higher accuracy of one of the models.

Contents

List of Figures	V
List of Tables	VI
List of Abbreviations	VII
1 Introduction	1
2 The Sun and its Structure	6
2.1 Basic Characteristics	6
2.2 The Structure of the Sun	7
2.3 Solar Activity and Solar Phenomena	10
3 Coronal Mass Ejections	13
3.1 Thomson Scattering	13
3.2 Observational Features of CMEs	13
3.3 Modelling of CMEs and ICMEs	15
3.3.1 The GCS Model	16
3.3.2 The DBM	19
3.3.3 The MODBM	22
4 Missions and Instrumentation	25
4.1 The Vigil Mission	25
4.2 The SOHO Mission	26
4.3 The STEREO Mission	27
4.4 The WIND Mission and its Instruments	29
4.5 Coronagraphs	29
4.5.1 LASCO/C2 and LASCO/C3	30
4.5.2 COR2	31
5 Events Studied	32
5.1 Event Selection	32
5.2 Data Sources and Data Processing	34
5.2.1 Python 3 Implementation of the GCS Model	34
5.2.2 In-Situ Solar Wind Data	35
5.3 Data Analysis	36
5.3.1 Geometric CME Modelling with the GCS Model	36
5.3.2 ICME Propagation Modelling	39
6 Results and Discussion	48
6.1 3D Modelling with the GCS Model	48
6.2 Determination of Propagation Model Input Parameters	52
6.3 ICME Arrival Times	56
7 Conclusion and Outlook	59
8 Bibliography	IX

A Appendix	1
A.1 Reconstructed Apex Heights and Corresponding Image Time Stamps Used in Velocity Determination	1
A.2 3D Reconstruction and Identification of an Event Predicted to Narrowly Miss the Earth	3

List of Figures

1	CME observation by COR2A on December 7th, 2020.	2
2	Schematic representation of the different parts of the Sun and solar phenomena.	7
3	Temperature and electron density models of the chromosphere and lower corona.	9
4	A butterfly diagram displaying the positions of sunspots recorded since May 1874 and the 11 year sunspot cycle.	11
5	Image of a three-part structure CME with a loop-like leading edge, a dark cavity and a bright core.	14
6	Face-on (left) and edge-on (right) view of the GCS model with drawn in parameters.	17
7	Position and orientation parameters of the GCS model (skeleton) in 3D space.	18
8	Comparison of the ambient solar wind speed models of the DBM and MODBM between 0 and 1 AU.	22
9	Comparison of the proton density models of the DBM and MODBM between 0 and 1 AU.	23
10	Artistic view of the INSTANT mission concept.	25
11	Schematic of the SOHO spacecraft with the instruments onboard.	27
12	Schematic of the ST-B spacecraft with the onboard instruments and features.	28
13	Design of the externally occulted Lyot coronagraph C2 mounted on the SOHO spacecraft.	30
14	Observations of a CME on January 7th, 2014 around 19.40 UT.	31
15	The GCS model applied to the observations of event UC1-CME-4 recorded by COR2B and C2.	37
16	The GCS model applied to the observations of event UC1-CME-3 recorded by COR2A and C3.	38
17	Velocity determination plot for event UC1-CME-4.	40
18	Velocity determination plot for event UC1-CME-3.	41
19	Determination of the EAR value for event UC1-CME-4.	42
20	In-situ solar wind data recorded with the WIND spacecraft between November 3rd and November 7th, 2021.	44
21	Comparison of the modelled 1D Earth-directed CME front propagations for event UC1-CME-4.	45
22	Comparison of the modelled 1D Earth-directed CME front propagations for event UC1-CME-3.	46
23	Determination of the EAR value for event UC1-CME-7.	3

List of Tables

1	List of basic solar parameters and their values.	6
2	Basic solar wind characteristics near Earth's orbit.	10
3	Basic characteristics of CMEs.	15
4	The CME events analysed in this work.	33
5	Results of the geometric CME modelling with the GCS model.	49
6	Results of the determination of necessary input parameters used by both propagation models in this work.	52
7	Results of the determination of model-specific input parameters of the two propagation models used in this work.	55
8	Arrival time prediction results from the propagation modelling with the DBM and the MODBM together with the ICME arrival times measured in-situ at L1.	57
9	Arrival time prediction results from the propagation modelling with the DBM and the MODBM compared to each other and to the ICME arrival times measured in-situ at L1.	58
10	The reconstructed GCS apex heights for the observations analysed in this work, accompanied by the time stamps of the respective images taken by COR2 and C2/C3.	2

List of Abbreviations

1D	One Dimensional
2D	Two Dimensional
3D	Three Dimensional
C1	LASCO Coronagraph 1
C2	LASCO Coronagraph 2
C3	LASCO Coronagraph 3
CAT	CME Analysis Tool
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
COR1	STEREO/SECCHI CORonagraph 1
COR2	STEREO/SECCHI CORonagraph 2
COR2A	COR2 onboard ST-A
COR2B	COR2 onboard ST-B
DBM	Drag-Based Model
EAR	Earth-directed height to Apex-directed height Ratio
EPACT	Energetic Particles: Acceleration, Composition and Transport
ESA	European Space Agency
FOV	Field of View
GCS	Graduated Cylindrical Shell
GUI	Graphical User Interface
ICME	Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejection
IDL	Interactive Data Language
INSTANT	INvestigation of Solar-Terrestrial Activity aNd Transients
L1	Lagrange Point 1
L4	Lagrange Point 4
L5	Lagrange Point 5
LASCO	Large Angle and Spectrometric COronagraph
MAGIC	MAGnetic Imager of the Corona
MHD	MagnetoHydroDynamics
MODBM	MODified Drag-Based Model
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
ODE	Ordinary Differential Equation

PHELIX	Polarising HELiospheric Imager eXplorer
SECCHI	Sun-Earth Connection Coronal and Heliospheric Investigation
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SMS	Solar Wind and Suprathermal Ion Composition Experiment
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SSN	relative SunSpot Number
ST-A	STEREO-Ahead
ST-B	STEREO-Behind
STEREO	Solar TERrestrial RELations Observatory
UC	Use Case

1 Introduction

Coronal mass ejections (CMEs) are large-scale releases of plasma and magnetic field from the Sun's corona that are explosively ejected into the heliosphere. They were discovered in images taken by the coronagraph onboard the seventh Orbiting Solar Observatory (OSO-7) in 1971 (Tousey, 1973). CMEs are optically thin structures that are only visible through the light of the photosphere scattered by free electrons. In the imaging of CMEs, this mechanism, known as Thomson scattering, is therefore exploited (Chen, 2011). Thousands of CMEs have already been captured by coronagraphs onboard successful space missions.

Research into space weather, i.e. the influence of the Sun and other cosmic sources on the interplanetary space and the Earth, is currently of greater interest than ever before and of great relevance for our modern, high-tech society (Bothmer and Zhukov, 2007). Within this research field, influences of solar phenomena such as the solar wind, flares and solar energetic particles (SEPs) are studied. This includes CMEs as well, which are one of the most important solar phenomena influencing space weather. They can occur as often as daily, with the frequency of their occurrence tending to follow the 11-year solar cycle (Webb and Howard, 1994). It is known that Earth-directed CMEs can have a direct impact on navigation systems, power grids, aviation and space missions, for example (Schrijver et al., 2015).

Due to the risks that CMEs pose to our society, the accurate forecast of certain arrival parameters is of great importance. The arrival time of the CMEs and their arrival speed are two of the most important parameters predicted. Current methods of operational space weather forecasting rely largely on assets located at the Lagrange point 1 (L1) viewpoint, in geocentric orbit, or on the ground. Because of that, the forecast can effectively only be made from a single point of view. As a result, important CME measurements suffer from projection effects because of the light emission being optically thin (Burkepile et al., 2004). For these forecasts, images from the coronagraphs onboard the Solar and Heliospheric Observatory (SOHO) satellite, which is positioned in a halo orbit around L1 along the Sun-Earth line, are used. The SOHO mission (Domingo et al., 1995) was developed in a collaborative effort by the European Space Agency (ESA) and National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA).

Long-term observations of CMEs from multiple viewpoints were made possible by the

Figure 1: CME observation by COR2A on December 7th, 2020. The observation times (UT) are as follows: 16:24 (top left), 16:39 (top center), 16:54 (top right), 17:24 (bottom left), 17:39 (bottom center), 17:54 (bottom right). The CME develops according to the classical three-part structure and has a well recognisable flux rope-like structure. The presented pictures are generated screenshots of images taken by NASA's ST-A, provided by [Helioviewer.org](https://www.helioviewer.org).

launch of the Solar TERrestrial RELations Observatory (STEREO) mission ([Kaiser et al., 2008](#)) in October 2006 developed by the NASA. It consists of two nearly identical satellites STEREO-Ahead (ST-A) (which recorded the images shown in Figure 1) and STEREO-Behind (ST-B) orbiting the Sun at different distances. It provided the first full view of the Sun. These multi-viewpoint observations have shown that the following effects can occur for single-viewpoint observed disk events: an overestimation of the CME mass ([Pluta et al., 2018](#)), an overestimation of CME widths and an underestimation of CME speeds (e.g., [Burkepile et al., 2004](#)). The accuracy of space weather forecasts, if they are based only on observations from L1, potentially suffers from these effects. The incorporation of STEREO observations into space weather prediction models has confirmed the utility of a viewpoint not on the Sun-Earth line, especially when

combined with complementary near-Earth observations. However, the drifting orbit of the STEREO mission is not optimal for consistent predictions. It would be better to place a spacecraft in the Lagrange point 5 (L5), 60° behind Earth in its orbit. Some major advantages of an L5 vantage point for operational space weather forecasting are: the possibility of 4 – 5 day advance warning of the eruptive potential of active regions and the tracking of interplanetary coronal mass ejections (ICMEs) through the inner heliosphere with the possibility of post-correction of forecasts. A number of L5 mission concepts have been developed to advance science and/or improve operational space weather forecasting, culminating in ESA’s proposed operational Lagrange space weather monitoring mission (now Vigil), currently being developed under the Space Safety Programme and scheduled for launch in the late 2020’s.

Within the project group of a consortium actively involved in the development of the Vigil mission and whose activities focus, for example, on the expected improvements in space weather forecasting in relation to the arrival of CMEs on Earth, the CME events that serve as the data set to be studied in this work were selected. In order to investigate the expected improvements in space weather forecasting, forecasts must be made with similar data that will be available after the launch of the Vigil mission, and their accuracy must be tested. For this purpose, L1 viewpoint data from the SOHO mission and, to represent data from the L5 viewpoint, data from the STEREO satellites are used, since these have been near L5 (or within a 30° range of the L5 Earth-Sun angle) for about 2.5 years each.

Many of the models used for space weather forecasting use three dimensional (3D) CME input parameters, such as the velocity or angular width of the CME, which are obtained from observations (Verbeke et al., 2019). Various models have been developed to acquire these parameters. In this work, the 3D reconstruction of the selected events is done in order to create a reference point for further analysis. The reconstruction is carried out using the Graduated Cylindrical Shell (GCS) modelling technique (Thernisien et al., 2006) and can be used at a later stage to also obtain the 3D CME input parameters for forecasting.

The precision of the orientation of the CMEs determined by the 3D modelling can be examined in more detail when compared to near-Earth solar wind data. CMEs that just miss the Earth cause less strong (or no) signatures in the solar wind data measured

by, for example, the WIND spacecraft. Therefore, this work also briefly compares whether the determined orientations match the signatures in the solar wind data for these events.

There is also a wide variety of propagation models used in space weather forecasting. The Drag-Based Model (DBM) (Vršnak et al., 2013) determines the CME propagation based on CME initial properties as well as the properties of the ambient solar wind and provides a quick application for predicting arrival times and impact speeds. While the reconstruction of the CME events is the main focus of this work, a first attempt is also made to improve the DBM by integrating more recent research results. A modified version called the Modified Drag-Based Model (MODBM) is therefore introduced. The arrival times of the CMEs predicted with the two models are also compared to the actual arrival times determined by measurements done by the WIND spacecraft.

The objective that is the focus of this work is the following.

- **The selected events are reconstructed from the L1 and L5 viewpoints simultaneously using the GCS modelling technique, thus providing a reference point for further analysis.**

Additionally, the following four objectives are addressed in this work.

- **In reconstructing CMEs that narrowly miss the Earth, an attempt is made to assess in more detail whether the application of the GCS reconstruction method leads to the accurate prediction of CME propagation directions.**
- **In a first attempt to incorporate recent research results concerning solar wind properties into the DBM, a new model, the MODBM, is introduced.**
- **Input parameters needed in order to perform propagation modelling using both models, the DBM and the MODBM, are determined.**
- **The ICME arrival times of the selected events are predicted via the DBM and the MODBM using the determined input parameters and finally, the results are compared to in-situ solar wind measurements.**

This work is organised as follows. Chapter 2 gives a brief overview about basic characteristics of the Sun and its structure. Moreover, the effects of solar activity are briefly described and solar phenomena are introduced. In Chapter 3, CMEs are discussed in detail. In addition to Thomson scattering and the observational features of CMEs, the reconstruction and propagation models used in this work are also introduced. Chapter 4 presents the spacecrafts and instruments whose recorded data is used for this work. The CME events examined in this work are introduced in Chapter 5. Furthermore, the 3D reconstruction modelling and the propagation modelling procedure are explained as well. In Chapter 6, the results of this work are presented and discussed critically. Finally, the findings are summarised and an outlook is given in Chapter 7.

2 The Sun and its Structure

Since this thesis deals with the analysis of solar phenomena, in particular with the analysis of CMEs, in this chapter fundamental aspects of the Sun, namely basic characteristics, its structure, atmosphere and activity phenomena, are presented.

2.1 Basic Characteristics

The Sun is a yellow main sequence dwarf star (G2V-type) and has an absolute magnitude of 4.8. About 4.6 billion years ago, the evolution of the Sun began with the gravitational collapse of an interstellar molecular cloud (Connelly et al., 2012). In about five billion years, the supply of hydrogen in the Sun's core will be exhausted, causing thermonuclear fusion to begin in a core-surrounding shell and the Sun to grow to a radius of $166 R_{\odot}$. Finally, in about 12.5 billion years, the Sun will have lost a significant portion of its mass and, after almost all of its fuel has been used up, have shrunk into a white dwarf approximately the size of Earth¹.

Table 1: List of basic solar parameters and their values. From Stix (2004, p. 2-9) and Carroll and Ostlie (2006, p. 364).

Quantity	Value
Distance to Earth	1 AU = 149597870(2) km
Mass	$1 M_{\odot} = 1.9889(3) \cdot 10^{30}$ kg
Radius	$1 R_{\odot} = 696342$ km
Density	$\bar{\rho} = 1.408$ g cm ⁻²
Surface gravitation	$g_{\odot} = 274$ m s ⁻²
Solar constant	$S = 1367(3)$ W m ⁻²
Luminosity	$L_{\odot} = 3.844(10) \cdot 10^{26}$ W
Composition	92.1% H, 7.8% He and 0.1% Metals
Surface Temperature	$T_{\text{eff}} = 5778(3)$ K
Rotation Period	25 d (Equator), 36 d (Poles)

Precise values of the Sun's fundamental parameters are essential for the development of

¹Article by David Taylor (last accessed September 2022):
<https://faculty.wcas.northwestern.edu/infocom/The%20Website/end.html>.

accurate models to describe observations and phenomena associated with our Sun, like CMEs (see Section 3.3). Many basic parameters have been determined with increasing accuracy as a result of scientific progress in recent decades. Their values are listed in Table 1. The average distance between the Sun and Earth is defined as an astronomical unit (AU).

2.2 The Structure of the Sun

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the different parts of the Sun and solar phenomena. The internal structure of the Sun (core, radiative zone and convection zone) as well as its external structure (photosphere, chromosphere, and corona) are presented. Phenomena such as sunspots, coronal holes, flares and prominences are also displayed. From NASA, <https://imagine.gsfc.nasa.gov/science/objects/sun1.html>.

The gas of which the Sun is composed is compressed and held together by its own gravitational force. The plasma which is created at high temperatures in the solar interior extends over several layers of the Sun to its surface and beyond to the solar atmosphere. The Sun consists of eight regions that are clearly defined by the predominant mode of energy transfer and fundamental thermodynamic as well as magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) parameters (Kivelson and Russell, 1995): the core, the radiative zone, the

tachocline, the convection zone, the photosphere, the chromosphere, the transition region, and the corona, which (as well as solar phenomena) are shown in Figure 2 and are characterised below.

The core² is located in the centre of the Sun and extends to $0.25 R_{\odot}$. In the core, most of the Sun’s energy is generated by the fusion of hydrogen into helium at a temperature of 1.5×10^7 K and a density of $1.5 \times 10^5 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. The produced energy propagates outward and enters **the radiative zone** surrounding the core and extending to about $0.7 R_{\odot}$. The radiative zone is characterized by the fact that radiation is the method of energy transport. The density drops from $2 \times 10^4 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ to 200 kg m^{-3} along this layer, and the temperature drops from 7×10^6 K to about 2×10^6 K. Because the radiative zone is so dense, a single photon takes thousands of years to eventually reach the next layer, **the tachocline** (also known as **the interface layer**). While “discovered in the 1980s, the tachocline is now thought to play a fundamental role in the solar dynamo because it combines substantial radial and horizontal shear while being at the interface between the convection zone and the radiation zone” (Garaud, 2020, p. 1).

The convection zone reaches up to $1 R_{\odot}$ (the solar “surface”). The temperature drops from about 2×10^6 K at the base of the convection zone to 5700 K at the visible surface, where the density is only $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$. In the convection zone, the predominant mode of energy transport changes from radiation to convection, leading to the formation of granulations visible on the photosphere (Kivelson and Russell, 1995).

The photosphere³, located at $1 R_{\odot}$, is about 100 km thick and is defined as the surface of the Sun. The photosphere is the coolest layer of the Sun, its temperature is around the effective temperature of the Sun, $T_{\text{eff}} = 5778(3)$ K. The main phenomena of the photosphere imaged in white-light are granules, dark sunspots and bright faculae. This layer is the first layer of the solar atmosphere, which is highly inhomogenous, dynamic and time-varying.

The chromosphere extends up to a height of about 1600 km above the photosphere and is 10000 times fainter in brightness than the solar surface (Carroll and Ostlie, 2006, p. 364-365). In the chromosphere⁴, the temperature increases again from 6000 K to

²Article by Dr. D. H. Hathaway: <https://solarscience.msfc.nasa.gov/interior.shtml> (last accessed August 2022).

³Article by Dr. D. H. Hathaway: <https://solarscience.msfc.nasa.gov/surface.shtml> (last accessed August 2022).

⁴Article by Dr. D. H. Hathaway: <https://solarscience.msfc.nasa.gov/chromos.shtml> (last accessed August 2022).

Figure 3: Temperature and electron density models of the chromosphere and lower corona. The electron density is indicated by n_e ; n_{H_0} denotes the neutral hydrogen density, since the plasma in the chromosphere is only partially ionised. From [Aschwanden \(1966, sec. 1.6\)](#).

20000 K while the density decreases. This is presented in Figure 3. The chromosphere can be well observed in the H_α line, the brightest spectral line of excited hydrogen in visible light, showing the chromosphere’s typical reddish colour ([Carroll and Ostlie, 2006, p. 364-365](#)).

Above the chromosphere, the temperature rapidly increases to 10^6 K (see Figure 3) within a thin transition layer called **transition region**⁵. At these temperatures, the hydrogen is ionised so that the light emitted from this area is primarily emitted by carbon, oxygen and silicon ions.

The corona forms the largest part of the solar atmosphere and is even 100 times fainter than the chromosphere. The coronal temperature reaches values of up to 5×10^6 K and it has a particle density of 10^{15} m^{-3} . Due to the high temperatures, only the heaviest elements can keep some of their electrons. The highly ionised coronal plasma emits extreme ultraviolet (EUV) radiation and X-rays. The corona is divided into the components K, F and E according to different types of radiation: the **K**(continuum)-corona, the **F**(Fraunhofer)-corona and the **E**(Emission)-corona ([Carroll and Ostlie, 2006, p. 366-370](#)). In addition to large Doppler shifts of the absorption lines from the photosphere, the K-corona also exhibits Thomson scattering (see Section 3.1) leading

⁵Article by Dr. D. H. Hathaway: https://solarscience.msfc.nasa.gov/t_region.shtml (last accessed August 2022).

to continuum radiation.

The interplanetary space is filled with **the solar wind**⁶, a continuous outflow of coronal plasma and magnetic field from the Sun. The solar wind gives rise to a region in space known as **the heliosphere**⁷. The studies of the German astronomer [Biermann \(1951\)](#) led to the discovery of the solar wind. Two types of solar wind can be distinguished based on their different origins, speeds, and compositions. The slow solar wind has low speeds and a particle composition similar to the corona. During solar minimum, the slow solar wind originates from the heliospheric stream near the equator and during solar maximum, from the tips of helmet streamers. The fast solar wind has high speeds, is less dense, and usually arises from coronal holes. The composition of the particles in the fast solar wind corresponds more to the photosphere of the Sun ([Bothmer and Zhukov, 2007](#), sec. 3.2.1). Some characteristics of the slow and the fast solar wind near the Earth are listed in Table 2. The solar rotation leads to a toroidal spiraling of the solar wind flowing radially outward. These spirals are known as Parker spirals ([Parker, 1958](#)). As a consequence, the solar wind strikes the Earth at an angle of about 45°. The spiral effect is less intense for the fast than for the slow solar wind due to the difference in speed. The two types of the solar wind can collide, which can trigger shock waves.

Table 2: Basic solar wind characteristics near Earth’s orbit. Adapted from [Schwenn \(1990\)](#).

Characteristic	Slow Solar Wind	Fast Solar Wind
Speed w	$\lesssim 450 \text{ km s}^{-1}$	$450 - 800 \text{ km s}^{-1}$
Proton density n_p	$\sim 7 - 10 \text{ cm}^{-3}$	$\sim 3 \text{ cm}^{-3}$
Composition	$\sim 94\% \text{ H, } 4\% \text{ He, minor ions and same number of electrons}$	$\sim 95\% \text{ H, } 5\% \text{ He, minor ions and same number of electrons; great variability}$
Magnetic field strength B	$\sim 4 \text{ nT}$	$\sim 5 \text{ nT}$

2.3 Solar Activity and Solar Phenomena

The Sun is the most powerful source of energy in our solar system and is subject to constant fluctuations. Sunspots, active regions, flares, large twisted plasma loops,

⁶Article by Dr. D. H. Hathaway: <https://solarscience.msfc.nasa.gov/SolarWind.shtml> (last accessed August 2022).

⁷Article by Dr. D. H. Hathaway: <https://solarscience.msfc.nasa.gov/Heliosphere.shtml> (last accessed August 2022).

Figure 4: At the top, a butterfly diagram showing the positions of the spots recorded since May 1874 by the Royal Greenwich Observatory is shown. The Sunspots are concentrated along two latitude bands around the equator and decrease in absolute maximum latitudes while the solar cycle progresses. At the bottom, the 11-year sunspot cycle is presented. From NASA - Dr. D. H. Hathaway: <https://solarscience.msfc.nasa.gov/SunspotCycle.shtml>.

prominence eruptions, CMEs and solar energetic particles are some of various solar activity phenomena discovered in the past. Phenomena capable of causing a geomagnetic disturbance are called geoeffective phenomena. Following a periodicity of about 11 years, the activity of the Sun increases and decreases. This is the so-called solar cycle. At the end of each cycle, the Sun’s global magnetic field reverses polarity.

Sunspots are dark regions appearing and disappearing on the solar surface. They usually emerge in groups. Sunspots can visually indicate **active regions**, which are areas with especially strong magnetic fields, but not all active regions produce sunspots⁸. Active regions, when imaged using different filters in the extreme ultraviolet at higher altitudes above the photosphere, appear as bright regions. Schwabe (1844) systematically recorded sunspots and discovered a pattern called the “Schwabe cycle” with a period around 11 years (see Figure 4). For systematic records, Wolf (1856) introduced the relative sunspot number (SSN), more commonly known today as the international sunspot number S_n . It is composed of the observed number of sunspots

⁸Article by the University Corporation for Atmospheric Research (UCAR): <https://scied.ucar.edu/learning-zone/sun-space-weather/sun-active-region> (last accessed September 2022).

n_s , the number of sunspot groups n_g and a scaling coefficient k via

$$SSN = 10k \cdot (n_s + n_g)$$

where k encompasses the observation conditions, telescope aperture, and the experience of the observer. It is common to use the 13-month smoothed monthly total sunspot number for calculations regarding events that last over a longer period of time.

As a result of solar activity, magnetic energy is transformed into other forms of energy which drive solar phenomena. Active regions can, for example, change their brightness abruptly, producing a solar X-ray **flare**. These processes in active regions occur preferentially at lower heliographic latitudes as the solar cycle progresses, following the butterfly pattern of sunspots (see Figure 4). Flares are characterised by explosive, time-limited light emission in a wide range of the electromagnetic spectrum. They were first observed by [Carrington \(1859\)](#), who took notice of two bright patches within a sunspot group. **CMEs** are large-scale coronal transients propagating outward into space (see Section 3), which can be geoeffective if they are directed towards the Earth. CMEs are often associated with flares and to a greater extent also with **prominence eruptions** ([Webb and Hundhausen, 1987](#)). Figure 2 illustrates a flare and an eruptive prominence.

SEPs (also known as “solar proton events” or “proton storms”) are related to CME and flare events and can also cause disturbances at Earth. They consist of highly energetic particles and are formed during the eruption phase of an intense CME or flare ([Droege and Schlickeiser, 1986](#)). The composition of SEPs is similar to that of the solar wind, but SEPs move at near-relativistic speeds. They interact with the Earth’s magnetosphere by being directed towards the poles, then penetrating the magnetosphere and ionising the lower ionosphere ([Richard et al., 2002](#)).

3 Coronal Mass Ejections

In this chapter, the characteristics of CMEs and the physical principle on the basis of which they can be observed are described in more detail. Also, models used in modern research that attempt to reproduce the structure and propagation of CMEs in space are introduced.

3.1 Thomson Scattering

The mechanism of Thomson scattering is exploited in the imaging of CMEs since CMEs are optically thin structures visible only via photospheric white-light scattered by free electrons. Thomson scattered light can provide information about basic CME characteristics (see Section 3.2, Table 3) such as its mass (Colaninno and Vourlidas, 2009). Inelastic scattering by free or quasi-free charged particles is generally described by Compton scattering. For visible light, where the kinetic energy of the electron and the frequency of the photon are conserved during the collision, the low-energy limit of Compton scattering is achieved and the collision is elastic. This particular case is called Thomson scattering (Jackson, 1975). It occurs if the following two conditions apply (Howard and Tappin, 2009): (1) The separation of the scattering particles must be large in contrast to the coherence length of the radiated light, and (2) the rest mass energy of the scattering particle has to be significantly high compared to the photon energy. The scattering processes in the Sun's corona and in the solar wind in the heliosphere satisfy both conditions.

3.2 Observational Features of CMEs

CMEs are outburst of coronal plasma bound in large flux rope-like magnetic structures. They occur as a change in coronal structure and manifest as new and discrete white-light features on a time scale of a few minutes to hours, which agrees with the definition according to Hundhausen et al. (1984). Early models of CMEs in the corona included expanding loops, like the model developed by Low et al. (1982), which investigated the quasi-static evolution of an ascending loop-shaped CME. Aulanier (2013) gives an overview of the numerous models for eruptive phenomena developed over 40 years. The current understanding is that CMEs are driven by the reconnection of coronal magnetic

field lines (Forbes, 2000). They are accelerated beyond the gravitational influence of the Sun and hurled into the heliosphere. The material that propagates in the solar wind as the interplanetary counterpart of a CME at the Sun is called ICME (Cane and Richardson, 2003). ICMEs that are faster than the surrounding (ambient) solar wind are slowed down, while ICMEs that are slower are accelerated. CME propagation models, such as those described in the following chapters, attempt to reproduce this behaviour.

Thousands of CMEs have already been recorded using coronagraphs (see Section 4.5)

Figure 5: Image of a three-part structure CME with a loop-like leading edge, a dark cavity and a bright core as seen by C2 on December 2nd, 2002. From Colaninno (2012).

from various space missions, such as the SOHO satellite and the STEREO probes. Some of the CME characteristics and observational features revealed from these observations are listed in Table 3. In general, the morphology of a CME is described by the classical “three-part” structure (Cremades and Bothmer, 2004). They consist of a bright leading front curved in a loop with its bases anchored to the solar surface, followed by a dark cavity surrounding a bright core of prominence material (see Figure 5).

Sometimes, CMEs are seen as outburst surrounding the occulting disk in coronagraph observations. These CMEs are then called “Halos” (or “Halo-CMEs”). The most common interpretation of Halos by Howard et al. (1982) is based on projection effects and defines Halos as eruptive events near the centre of the Sun directed towards or away from the observer. When only part of the occulter is surrounded, the event is

Table 3: Basic characteristics of CMEs. From [Bothmer \(2006\)](#).

Quantity	Value
Speed	$\sim 300 - 3000 \text{ km s}^{-1}$
Mass	$5 \cdot 10^{12} - 5 \cdot 10^{13} \text{ kg}$
Kinetic Energy	$10^{23} - 10^{24} \text{ J}$
Angular Width	$\sim 24^\circ - 72^\circ$
Occurrence Frequency	$\sim 0.5 - 6 \text{ per day (solar min. - solar max.)}$

called a partial Halo.

[Sheeley et al. \(1985\)](#) found that interplanetary shock waves often occur along with large ICMEs, which are considered to be their source. Shock waves driven by fast ICMEs occur when the speed of the ICME greatly exceeds the speed of the surrounding solar wind ([Aschwanden, 1966](#), Chap. 17.9.3). ICMEs then propagate into space as an interplanetary shock in front of a sheath region followed by a magnetic cloud ([Burlaga et al., 1981](#)). These features can be detected in the in-situ solar wind data measured, for example, by the WIND spacecraft (see Section 4.4). The characteristics of these shocks depend on the CME morphology, but they are usually characterised by a sharp, temporally short increase in multiple solar wind plasma parameters in measured solar wind data, such as the magnetic field strength, the proton speed, the proton density and the temperature of the plasma.

ICMEs directed towards Earth are the most geoeffective solar phenomena ([Bothmer and Zhukov, 2007](#)). Due to their high velocities combined with the strong magnetic fields they carry, they cause distortions in the Earth’s magnetosphere. They can trigger strong geomagnetic storms on Earth, posing a serious threat to space systems, communications and navigation. Therefore, predictions of the arrival of CMEs and best possible models for their description are of particular interest.

3.3 Modelling of CMEs and ICMEs

In order to forecast ICME arrival times and impacts, an ICME propagation model is needed. Some ICME propagation models, such as the DBM (see Section 3.3.2), use 3D CME input parameters, like the velocity or angular width of the CME, which are obtained from observations ([Verbeke et al., 2019](#)). Recently, the magnetic B_z component has become the focus of increasing research interest (e.g., [Jin et al. 2017](#),

Möstl et al. 2018), but will not be discussed further in this work. Various methods and models have been developed to acquire these parameters. Some examples are the two dimensional (2D) Ice-Cream Cone (ICC) model (see Xue et al., 2005) and the CME Analysis Tool (CAT) (see Millward et al., 2013). Like the CAT, which uses a tear-drop like model to reconstruct CMEs, the GCS model developed by Thernisien et al. (2006) defines the topology of an ascending CME structure at an early stage of its development and assumes a constant CME speed during the development. The GCS model (see Section 3.3.1) is used in this work, since it includes a larger number of adjustable parameters compared to the two models already mentioned. It also reproduces the observable flux rope-like shape of CMEs.

There is also a wide variety of propagation models. The models are usually built around different assumptions and simplifications concerning the physical processes. Besides drag-based models, there are empirical models, expansion speed models, physics-based models, and time-dependent MHD models. Zhao and Dryer (2014) discuss the types of models in detail. In this work, the DBM is used because its assumptions allow an analytical solution and it provides a quick application for predicting arrival times and impact speeds of ICMEs.

In an attempt to optimise the DBM, a modified version of it called the MODBM is also introduced. This version makes use of new scientific findings to describe the ambient solar wind density and the ambient solar wind speed more accurately between 0 and 1 AU. The equation of motion can then no longer be solved analytically.

3.3.1 The GCS Model

The GCS modelling technique (Thernisien et al., 2006) is empirically defined and used to reconstruct the large-scale 3D geometry from coronagraph images for flux rope-like CMEs. It was developed based on the findings of Cremades and Bothmer (2004) and is used in this work to derive CME shapes, orientations and kinematics.

The GCS geometry (see Figure 6) consists of two cone shaped legs connected to a tubular section whose radius decreases towards the ends. As a result, the shape is reminiscent of a croissant. The centre of the tube is represented in Figure 6 by the dash-dotted line, and the outline of the model is represented by solid lines. The circular

Figure 6: Face-on (left) and edge-on (right) view of the GCS model with drawn in parameters a , r , α and h (see Equation (1) and Equation (2)). A representation of the electron density distribution $N_e(d)$ (see Equation (4)) is shown in the upper right corner utilising the parameters d , σ_t and σ_l . From [Thernisien et al. \(2006\)](#).

annulus of the tubular section has a varying radius a which is determined by

$$a(r) = \kappa r \quad (1)$$

where r represents the distance between the centre of the Sun and a point at the outer edge of the GCS model shell. κ is the aspect ratio of the two orthogonal CME sizes a and r and a constant which must be determined individually for each CME. This parameter κ represents the constraint of self-similar expansion for CMEs described with the GCS model. The leg ends spring from the centre of the Sun and the angle between the two legs is twice the half angle α . By using the leg height h and the already described parameters of the model, one can determine the height of the leading edge of the model relative to the centre of the Sun, also called the apex height h_{apex} , via

$$h_{\text{apex}} = h \frac{1 + \kappa}{1 - \kappa^2} \frac{1 + \sin(\alpha)}{\cos(\alpha)}. \quad (2)$$

Additionally, more parameters need to be defined describing the position and orientation of the flux rope in 3D space (see Figure 7). The Carrington longitude ϕ_C and heliographic latitude θ are commonly used to dictate the exact position of a projection (e.g., of a CME apex) on the solar surface. Moreover, rotating the model will result in a non-zero tilt angle γ . For $\gamma = 0^\circ$, the orientation of the tubular section of the model is parallel to the solar equator and for $\gamma = \pm 90^\circ$, it is perpendicular.

Another description of longitude, which is often used in the context of describing the

Figure 7: Position and orientation parameters ϕ_C , θ and γ of the GCS model (skeleton) in 3D space. From [Thernisien et al. \(2009\)](#).

orientation of CMEs (as in this work), is the Stonyhurst longitude ϕ . The Stonyhurst coordinate system remains fixed with respect to the Earth while the Sun rotates synodically beneath it; its origin is at the intersection of the solar equator and the central meridian as seen from the Earth. In contrast to that, the Carrington system is not fixed with respect to the Earth but rotates along with solar surface. Therefore, Carrington longitude is offset from Stonyhurst longitude by a time-dependent scalar value given by the equation

$$\phi_C = \phi + L_0 \quad (3)$$

where L_0 is the Carrington longitude of the central meridian as seen from Earth. The latitude θ is defined the same in the Stonyhurst and Carrington coordinate systems (Thompson, 2006).

In order for the model to be compared to the white-light structure of a CME on the coronagraph images, a synthetic white-light coronagraph image must be created from the GCS model. A ray-tracing code that allows the determination of Thomson scattering by electrons along the line of sight of the observer needs an electron density profile applied to the model (Thernisien, 2011). In this case, the profile is described by an asymmetric Gaussian like function $N_e(d)$ which takes in the already introduced radius a and an electron density factor N_e and is given by

$$N_e(d) = N_e \exp \left[- \left(\frac{d - a}{\sigma_s} \right)^2 \right] \quad \text{with} \quad \sigma_s = \begin{cases} \sigma_t, & \text{if } d < a \\ \sigma_l, & \text{if } d \geq a \end{cases} . \quad (4)$$

Here σ_{trailing} (or σ_t) is the width of the Gaussian function inside the shell of the model, while σ_{leading} (or σ_l) is the width outside the shell.

3.3.2 The DBM

The DBM (Vršnak et al., 2013) is a one dimensional (1D) model determining the heliospheric propagation of ICMEs. It builds on the assumption that the driving Lorentz force, which is launching a CME, strongly decreases in its influence in the upper corona and that beyond a certain distance the interaction of the ICME and the ambient solar wind becomes a dominant factor in the propagation dynamics. The result of this interaction is an MHD drag caused by collisionless transfer of momentum and energy between the ICME and the ambient solar wind. Furthermore, a quadratic form for the drag acceleration given by

$$a = -\gamma (v - w) |v - w| \quad (5)$$

is considered where v is the instantaneous ICME velocity, w is the (constant) ambient solar wind speed and γ is the drag parameter. Depending on the distance r of the

ICME from the centre of the Sun, the equation of motion reads

$$\frac{d^2r}{dt^2} = -\gamma(r) \left(\frac{dr}{dt} - w(r) \right) \left| \frac{dr}{dt} - w(r) \right|. \quad (6)$$

Assuming a constant drag parameter ($\gamma = \text{const.}$), its analytic solution can be written as

$$r(t) = \pm \frac{1}{\gamma} \ln [1 \pm \gamma (v_0 - w)] + wt + r_0 \quad (7)$$

for a given initial ICME velocity v_0 ($v_{t=0}$) at an initial radial distance r_0 ($r_{t=0}$). Generally, the value of the drag parameter, given by

$$\gamma(r) = \frac{c_d A \rho_w}{M}, \quad (8)$$

changes with distance (see Section 3.3.3). In its simplest form, the model makes the assumption that the drag parameter is constant resulting from the following assumptions: at sufficiently large distances $r > 20 R_\odot$ the dimensionless drag coefficient c_d is constant ($c_d = \text{const.}$), the ICME cross-section A follows $A \propto r^2$, the ambient solar wind density ρ_w follows $\rho_w \propto 1/r^2$ and the ICME mass M is constant ($M = \text{const.}$) (Vršnak et al., 2013). Formulas and approximations for the individual parameters are presented in the following.

The cross-section A heavily depends on the model used for the 3D CME reconstruction. When the GCS model is applied, A can be determined most accurately by performing numerical calculations as detailed in Thernisien (2011). However, a faster, analytical calculation providing only slightly less accurate results is used in this work: The GCS cross-section A depending on the distance of the ICME apex from the Sun r [km] is obtained by the approximation with the base area of an elliptic cone at the flux rope centre height r_c with the two half angles α and δ of the two main axis via

$$A(r) = \pi r_c^2 \tan(\alpha) \tan(\delta) \quad (9)$$

where $\delta = \arcsin(\kappa)$ and $r_c = \frac{r}{(1+\kappa)}$ (Pluta, 2018, p. 111). The parameters α and κ can be obtained from the GCS model introduced in Section 3.3.1.

Pluta et al. (2018) were the first to use the GCS model on a large scale to estimate CME

masses and to analyse the most suitable CME characteristics for this purpose. They “propose that the following empirical correlation between the CME masses and the CME velocities is most suited to estimate the mass of intense CMEs from coronagraph images” (Pluta et al., 2018, p. 11):

$$\log_{10}(M) = 3.4 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot v_{\text{apex}} + 15.479 \quad (10)$$

where M is the CME mass and v_{apex} is the velocity of the CME apex (see Section 3.3.1). This formula enables a quick determination of the CME mass in the context of space weather forecasts. It is best applicable for “disk events”, characterised by CMEs originating from the vicinity of an observer’s centre of the solar disc, propagating towards or away from the observer along the Sun-observer line.

The ambient solar wind density $\rho_w(r)$ is calculated via

$$\rho_w(r) = m_p n_0(r), \quad (11)$$

using the proton mass $m_p = 1.67262192369 \times 10^{-27} \text{ kg}^9$ and the particle density $n_0(r)$. The particle density can be modelled as a function of the radial distance from the Sun $n_0(r)$ given by

$$n_0(r) \simeq 3.3 \cdot 10^5 [\text{cm}^{-3}] \cdot \frac{1}{r^2}. \quad (12)$$

This is the first order approximation of the empirical solar wind model (Leblanc et al., 1998).

As MHD simulations have shown, the last remaining parameter, the dimensionless drag coefficient c_d , converges to $c_d = 1$ shortly after $12 R_{\odot}$ (Cargill, 2004). So for propagation calculations involving the DBM that start after this lower boundary, the approximation is therefore valid.

Lastly, it is common to substitute γ (see Equation (8)) with

$$\Gamma = \gamma \cdot 10^7 [\text{km}^{-1}]. \quad (13)$$

⁹Published by the CODATA Task Group on Fundamental Constants:
<https://physics.nist.gov/cgi-bin/cuu/Value?mp> (last accessed August 2022).

The assumptions that put the model in its simplest form yield values, if statistically derived for magnetic ejecta, in the range of $\Gamma = 0.1 - 2 \text{ km}^{-1}$ (Vršnak et al., 2013).

3.3.3 The MODBM

The MODBM is a modified version of the DBM, also with the aim of determining the heliospheric propagation of ICMEs, specifically in the range from 0 to 1 AU. Due to the complexity of the DBM (see Section 3.3.2), newer insights can be introduced at various points within the model. The foundation of the DBM remains intact within the MODBM, it assumes that the driving Lorentz force strongly decreases in its influence and that the interaction of the ICME and the ambient solar wind becomes a dominant factor beyond a certain distance. The form of the MHD drag acceleration caused by collisionless transfer of momentum and energy is again considered to be quadratic (see Equation (5)). Recent scientific findings are now being incorporated into the parameters of this acceleration; these are described below.

The ambient solar wind speed w follows according to Venzmer and Bothmer (2018) a

Figure 8: Comparison of the ambient solar wind speed models of the DBM and MODBM between 0 and 1 AU. The solar wind speed distribution w is assumed to be constant in the DBM and is shown for three different speeds, while the MODBM suggests two separate distributions for the slow and the fast solar wind.

distribution depending on solar distance r [AU] given by

$$w_{\text{med}}^{\text{slow}}(r) = 363 [\text{km s}^{-1}] \cdot r^{0.099} \quad \text{and} \quad w_{\text{med}}^{\text{fast}}(r) = 483 [\text{km s}^{-1}] \cdot r^{0.099} \quad (14)$$

for the slow and fast solar wind, respectively. These distributions differ significantly from the assumption that the ambient solar wind speed remains the same from 0 to 1 AU, which is used in the DBM. In Figure 8, a comparison of both models/assumptions is presented. The median is used to address seasonal variation because the distributions are based on yearly data.

In determining the drag parameter γ , given by Equation (8), the ambient solar wind density ρ_w is composed of the ambient particle density multiplied by the proton mass (see Equation (11)). The DBM makes use of the first order approximation of the empirical solar wind model. In accordance with newer scientific findings, the proton density relation depending on solar distance r [AU] and the SSN (see Section 2.3) derived by [Venzmer and Bothmer \(2018\)](#) (used in the MODBM) reads

$$n_{\text{med}}(SSN, r) = (0.0038 [\text{cm}^{-3}] \cdot SSN + 4.50 [\text{cm}^{-3}]) \cdot r^{-2.11}. \quad (15)$$

Here, too, the median is used for similar reasons as before. Figure 9 presents a comparison between the density models of the DBM and the MODBM.

For the further determination of the drag parameter γ , the other parameters are

Figure 9: Comparison of the proton density models of the DBM and MODBM between 0 and 1 AU. The proton density relation in the MODBM is presented for two different values of the SSN. In both plots, the density is plotted logarithmically against the distance from the Sun r . A zoomed-in version of the plot (from 0.34 to 1 AU) is shown on the right.

calculated in congruence with the DBM. The cross-section A is determined according to Equation (9), the CME mass M according to Equation (10) and Γ according to Equation (13). For the dimensionless drag coefficient c_d , it is again assumed that it converges to $c_d = 1$ shortly after $12 R_{\odot}$ ([Cargill, 2004](#)).

Crucially, the MODBM uses neither a constant drag parameter γ nor a constant solar wind speed w (as was the case with the DBM) due to the new dependencies on the distance to the Sun r . Because of that, the equation of motion (see Equation (6)) can only be solved numerically.

4 Missions and Instrumentation

In this chapter, the three missions whose recorded data is used for this work are presented. For the 3D reconstruction of CMEs and the study of their kinematics, data from coronagraph instruments onboard SOHO and STEREO is used. The arrival times of ICMEs and information about the solar wind is later determined via various instruments onboard the WIND spacecraft. The analyses serve to prepare for the future Vigil Mission, the concept of which is also presented in this chapter.

4.1 The Vigil Mission

Figure 10: Artistic view of the INSTANT mission concept. The monitoring of space weather phenomena is illustrated. From Lavraud et al. (2016).

Vigil is a mission to the L5 in the Sun-Earth system in development at the ESA and was planned to launch in the mid-2020's¹⁰ (now late-2020's). Vigil is a modified and renamed version of the Investigation of Solar-Terrestrial Activity and Transients (INSTANT) mission concept proposed by Lavraud et al. (2016) designed to enable measurements of coronal magnetic fields (see Figure 10) and determination of CME kinematics. In addition, INSTANT could track the processes that drive space weather from their origin to the Earth. While the INSTANT mission concept is primarily geared towards use for

¹⁰Official Vigil mission website: https://www.esa.int/Space_Safety/Vigil (last accessed August 2022)

scientific purposes, Vigil is intended to function as a space weather warning system in the future. The only other mission to perform measurements near L5 was the STEREO mission (see Section 4.3).

The baseline payload consists of five complementary instruments, namely the Magnetic Imager of the Corona (MAGIC) coronagraph, the Polarising Heliospheric Imager Explorer (PHELIX) and three in-situ instruments (Lavraud et al., 2016). The MAGIC coronagraph would perform measurements of the coronal magnetic field from $1.15 R_{\odot}$ to $3 R_{\odot}$, while the PHELIX brings about wide-angle imaging in the white-light range with unprecedented polarisation capabilities. Additionally, the Magnetometer (MAG) measures the ambient magnetic field and the High Energy Particle Sensors (HEPS) instrument detects high energy electrons, protons and heavy ions. Lastly, the Proton and Alpha Sensor (PAS) measures the 3D ion velocity distribution functions and its moments, e.g density and temperature.

The mission design of INSTANT can be viewed as paving the way for more comprehensive or operational space weather missions at L5. In an effort to improve the space weather forecast from L5 and to create useful models for application to measurements of future missions in L5, this work analyses CME events singled out specifically in preparation for the Vigil mission in the associated ESA project (see Section 5.1).

4.2 The SOHO Mission

The SOHO mission (Domingo et al., 1995) was developed in a collaborative effort by the ESA and NASA and launched in December 1995. The principal scientific objectives of the mission include studying the solar interior, the shaping and heating of the corona and the solar wind. The spacecraft was placed in a halo orbit around L1 positioned along the Sun-Earth line, about 1.5 million kilometres from Earth, which allows for continuous observation of the Sun.

It is equipped with twelve instruments of which six are specifically designed to investigate the solar disk and atmosphere, schematically shown in Figure 11. One of the remote-sensing sets of instruments onboard is the Large Angle and Spectrometric Coronagraph (LASCO) (Brueckner et al., 1995) (see Section 4.5.1).

The spacecraft was nearly lost in June of 1998 due to loss of contact, but could be

Figure 11: Schematic of the SOHO spacecraft with the instruments onboard. From [Domingo et al. \(1995\)](#).

located and put back into operation five months later¹¹. SOHO has already observed two 11-year solar cycles and is still in operation.

4.3 The STEREO Mission

The STEREO mission ([Kaiser et al., 2008](#)) developed by NASA was successfully launched in October 2006 and developed to investigate the causes and mechanisms of CME initiation and to track the propagation of CMEs through the inner heliosphere to Earth. It consists of two nearly identical satellites ST-A and ST-B, both equipped with a set of optical, radio and in-situ particles and fields instruments (see Figure 12). One of the four instrument suits onboard is the Sun-Earth Connection Coronal and Heliospheric Investigation (SECCHI) ([Howard et al., 2008](#)) suite containing two coronagraphs, an extreme ultra violet imager and a heliospheric imager. The combined instrumentation allows for the 3D tracking of CME white-light signatures from the Sun to Earth. For this work, images taken with the STEREO/SECCHI Coronagraph 2 (COR2) on both spacecrafts are used (see Section 4.5.2).

¹¹Press release published by NASA on December 2nd, 2020 (last accessed August 2022): <https://www.nasa.gov/feature/goddard/2020/esanasa-s-sun-observing-soho-mission-celebrates-a-quarter-century-in-space>

In order to get a stereoscopic view of the Sun and its corona, ST-A is on an orbit closer

Figure 12: Schematic of the ST-B spacecraft with the onboard instruments and features. Small differences to ST-A are that the arrangement of the long antennas used for solar wind measurements is changed. From Kaiser et al. (2008).

to the Sun than ST-B's orbit and thus flying ahead of Earth, while ST-B is trailing behind Earth. The separation angle between ST-A and ST-B increases by about 44° to 45° per year, providing a full view of the Sun for the first time on February 6th, 2011¹². On their trajectory orbiting around the Sun, the STEREO spacecrafts drifted through Lagrange point 4 (L4) and L5 in the Earth-Sun-system¹³. ST-B was within 30° of the L5 Earth-Sun angle from August 2008 to January 2011 and ST-A was within a similar angular range from July 2019 to May 2022. The CME events (and especially the Halo-events) captured by ST-B and ST-A in the respective periods are of particular interest in this work. That is because the analysis of these events is similar to the analysis that will take place for events recorded by the future Vigil mission.

After a planned hard reset, the contact to ST-B was lost on October 1st, 2014. The satellite lost its orientation and started to spin uncontrollably¹⁴. Due to this loss, much

¹²Press release published by NASA on February 6th, 2011 (last accessed August 2022):

http://www.nasa.gov/mission_pages/sterео/news/entire-sun.html

¹³Report on the STEREO spacecrafts visiting the Lagrange points (last accessed August 2022):

<https://svs.gsfc.nasa.gov/3591>

¹⁴ST-B Report on the website of the STEREO Science Center (last accessed August 2022):

http://sterео-ssc.nascom.nasa.gov/behind_status.shtml

scientific data for the 3D reconstruction of CMEs that occurred after 2014 was lost. Nevertheless, ST-A is still in operation today and provides solid solar research.

4.4 The WIND Mission and its Instruments

WIND is a spacecraft launched on November 1st, 1994 as part of the Global Geospace Science (GGS) program¹⁵. WIND was first placed in a Lissajous orbit around L1, but then inserted into a halo orbit around L1 in 2020. The science objectives of the WIND mission include providing complete studies of plasma, energetic particles and magnetic fields, as well as investigating basic processes that occur in the near-Earth solar wind. Moreover, it is providing baseline ecliptic plane observations for heliospheric missions. On the WIND spacecraft, the WAVES suite of instruments (Bougeret et al., 1995) provides measurements of radio and plasma wave phenomena. WAVES features, among other instruments, three orthogonally arranged magnetic search coils. It enables the monitoring of “the state of the solar wind as it approaches Earth” (Bougeret et al., 1995, p. 261) and the analysis of stream interactions.

The Energetic Particles: Acceleration, Composition and Transport (EPACT) investigation (von Rosenvinge et al., 1995) uses a combination of eight telescopes to observe energetic particles in a wide range of charge, mass and energy. For example, they allow the observation of SEPs which are dominated by energetic protons and are highly correlated with CMEs, as well as interplanetary shocks generated by CME and their composition.

The Solar Wind and Suprathermal Ion Composition Experiment (SMS) (Gloeckler et al., 1995) on WIND monitors the composition, the temperatures and the mean speeds of major solar wind ions. It operates at solar wind speeds from 175 km s^{-1} to 1280 km s^{-1} .

4.5 Coronagraphs

A coronagraph, first conceived by Bernard Lyot in 1930 (Lyot, 1939), is a type of telescope used to observe the solar corona by blocking light coming from the visible solar disk. The design of an externally occulted Lyot coronagraph is shown in Figure 13. Coronagraphs featuring externally mounted occulters produce lower stray light values compared to the values achieved with the internally occulted coronagraphs. However,

¹⁵NASA WIND homepage (last accessed August 2022): <https://wind.nasa.gov/index.php>

due to the diffraction limit, externally occulted coronagraphs cannot image the inner corona.

Figure 13: Design of the externally occulted Lyot coronagraph C2 mounted on the SOHO spacecraft. At the top, the beams of light come in from the left and generate a coronal image in the focal plane (F). The external occulter (D1) blocks the light coming from the solar disk, while the light of the corona can pass by it. The objective lens (O1) reduces scattering and projects an image of the external occulter onto the internal occulter (D2). Next, the light passes through the “Lyot stop” (A3); here, the diffracted light originating at the entrance aperture (A1) is stopped. The final image is formed by the camera objective (O3). Below, the suppression of stray light by the Lyot stop is shown. From [Brueckner et al. \(1995\)](#).

4.5.1 LASCO/C2 and LASCO/C3

The LASCO ([Brueckner et al., 1995](#)) set of instruments onboard the SOHO spacecraft is a triple coronagraph with nested, concentric annular fields of view (FOV). The three coronagraphs are externally occulted coronagraphs and use 1024x1024 charge-coupled device cameras as detectors. The LASCO Coronagraph 1 (C1) has not been operational since the loss and recuperation of the SOHO spacecraft. The design of the LASCO Coronagraph 2 (C2) (see Figure 13) and the LASCO Coronagraph 3 (C3) image the Sun’s corona between $1.5 R_{\odot}$ and $6 R_{\odot}$ and between $3.7 R_{\odot}$ and $30 R_{\odot}$, respectively. To allow for a gapless observation of CMEs with smooth transitions between observations, the coronagraphs onboard SOHO have overlapping FOV. The image cadence is 12 minutes.

By observing in three different linear polarization states and computing the polarized

brightness (Billings, 1966) the stray light of the instrument can be nearly eliminated. For this reason, each imaging sequence contains three images taken with different polarizers recorded in C2 and C3. In addition to the three polarizers, C2 and C3 are equipped with a combination of seven broadband and narrowband filters for the spectral range from 400 nm to 1050 nm.

4.5.2 COR2

COR2 is an externally occulted Lyot coronagraph developed based on the successful operating of C2 and C3 with a nested angular FOV of 8° , imaging the corona between $2.5 R_\odot$ and $15 R_\odot$. The STEREO/SECCHI Coronagraph 1 (COR1) (part of the same suite) is imaging the corona between $1.4 R_\odot$ and $4 R_\odot$ (Howard et al., 2008). The image cadence is 15 minutes, therefore three polarisation images are combined. Low-resolution total brightness images from COR2, computed onboard with a polarised image sequence, are continuously transmitted to Earth, which is useful for space weather purposes. The COR2 onboard ST-A (COR2A) and COR2 onboard ST-B (COR2B) telescopes are identical, except for different sizes of the occulters and different offsets of the coronagraphs boresight.

Figure 14 shows pictures of the same CME imaged by COR2A and COR2B. Also presented is an image of the CME taken by C3 from a near-Earth view.

Figure 14: Observations of a CME on January 7th, 2014 around 19.40 UT recorded by COR2B, C3 and COR2A. From Mays et al. (2015).

5 Events Studied

In this chapter, the CME events examined in this work are presented together with the selection criteria. Moreover, the processing of the data to be analysed and the programs used for the analysis are described. Finally, the procedure for 3D reconstruction with the GCS model and the difficulties encountered are presented, as well as the procedure for propagation modelling with the DBM and MODBM.

5.1 Event Selection

The CME events that serve as the data set to be studied in this work were selected within the project group of a consortium that actively participates in the development of the ESA's mission Vigil. The activity of this group is focused, for example, on the expected improvements in space weather forecasting concerning CME arrivals at Earth resulting from multi-viewpoint remote-sensing observations. RAL space¹⁶ as coordinator of this consortium provided a technical proposal detailing the overall project task structure.

One of the first tasks was to develop of a series of Use Cases (UCs) that address the various factors contributing to potential improvements in forecasting capabilities with remote-sensing instruments. Thus, different sets of UCs were prepared to demonstrate the impact of Vigil coronagraph/Heliospheric Imager (HI)/magnetograph data on (1) improving operational CME onset detection, (2) improving the operational prediction of ICMEs arrivals at Earth, (3) improving operational solar wind prediction and (4) improving forecasts of SEP events. In order to investigate how circumstances such as different viewpoints, coronagraph image resolutions or image cadences influence the results of the CME analysis, a total of seven UCs is considered. UC1, for which the CME events analysed in this work were specially selected, focuses on CME onset detection and characterisation from multiple vantage points (L1 and L5). The goal of examining UC1 is to demonstrate the impact of Vigil coronagraph data on improving the operational detection of CMEs and CME characterisation services.

The following conditions were included in the selection:

- The data should include a sufficiently large number of events to allow strong

¹⁶RAL space homepage (last accessed September 2022):
<https://www.ralspace.stfc.ac.uk/Pages/About-RAL-Space.aspx>

Table 4: The CME events analysed in this work. In addition to the CME-ID and the position relative to Earth of the STEREO spacecraft closest to L5, the time of entry into the FOV of COR2 is presented, which can oftentimes be specified more precisely than the actual CME launch time.

CME-ID	COR2 entry time (UT) y/m/d:hm	STEREO location [deg]
UC1-CME-1	2010/04/08:0439	-71 (ST-B)
UC1-CME-2	2020/10/26:0709	-59 (ST-A)
UC1-CME-3	2021/11/02:0253	-37 (ST-A)
UC1-CME-4	2010/05/24:1439	-70 (ST-B)
UC1-CME-5	2009/12/16:0339	-67 (ST-B)
UC1-CME-6	2011/06/14:0754	-93 (ST-B)
UC1-CME-7	2010/03/19:1224	-71 (ST-B)
UC1-CME-8	2010/04/03:1009	-71 (ST-B)
UC1-CME-9	2021/10/28:1553	-37 (ST-A)
UC1-CME-10	2020/12/07:1624	-57 (ST-A)
UC1-CME-11	2020/09/03:1849	-61 (ST-A)
UC1-CME-12	2021/02/10:1139	-56 (ST-A)
UC1-CME-13	2011/05/25:0454	-93 (ST-B)
UC1-CME-14	2011/07/11:1139	-93 (ST-B)
UC1-CME-15	2011/10/29:2159	-101 (ST-B)

conclusions about the beneficial use of the L5 data for CME detection and characterisation.

- A range of CMEs of different features and types should be examined so that the usefulness of the L5 data can be evaluated in the broadest possible framework.
- Halo-CMEs should be included to study how the data affects estimates of the CME's velocity and time of arrival at Earth.
- CMEs that narrowly miss Earth should also be in the data so that estimates of CME orientations/directions can be examined.

The data of the coronagraphs (see Section 4.5.1) onboard SOHO positioned in L1 is available from the 1990s until today. The STEREO satellites have been near L5 (and within 30° of the L5 Earth-Sun angle) for about 2.5 years each, as mentioned in Section 4.3. Thus, the data recorded by the STEREO coronagraphs (see Section 4.5.2) in these time frames can be analysed comparably to that of a coronagraph of the future Vigil mission in L5.

Taking into account the aspects mentioned above, the events listed in Table 4 were

selected in order to enable the investigation of the influences of L5 data. These are also the ones that will be analysed in this work.

5.2 Data Sources and Data Processing

5.2.1 Python 3 Implementation of the GCS Model

Originally, the GCS model was implemented in the Interactive Data Language (IDL)¹⁷ by Thernisien et al. (2006), who also developed a corresponding graphical user interface (GUI). The implementation is included in the *SolarSoft* software package (Freeland and Handy, 1998) and is named *scraytrace*¹⁸. SolarSoft was developed by members of the Yohkoh and SOHO mission teams and the NASA Solar Data Analysis Center (SDAC) in the 1990s as a collection of IDL libraries.

Freiherr von Forstner et al. (2021) implemented the GCS model and a corresponding GUI application for CME reconstruction in coronagraph images in *Python* based on *SunPy* (Barnes et al., 2020), a Python toolkit/library for use with solar images from various missions. In this work, the implementation is used via the GUI application. Freiherr von Forstner (2020) showed “that the Python version is implemented correctly and can be used for scientific purposes” by re-plotting a set of CMEs and comparing the results to the plots previously created by the IDL version (Freiherr von Forstner, 2020, sec. B.3).

The GCS GUI is started via the command line. The command line can be used to set start options and execute the following operations:

- Specify a date and time (UT) near which coronagraph images are to be downloaded:
"YYYY-MM-DD HH:MM"
- Specify the spacecraft or a combination of spacecrafts from which the observations are to be called (simultaneously): STA, STB, SOHO
- Specify the coronagraphs which are to be used for the selected spacecrafts: `–soho C2`, `–soho C3`, `–stereo COR1`, `–stereo COR2`

¹⁷Homepage: <https://www.l3harrisgeospatial.com/Software-Technology/IDL> (last accessed September 2022)

¹⁸Package: <https://hesperia.gsfc.nasa.gov/ssw/stereo/secchi/idl/scraytrace/> (last accessed September 2022)

- Specify whether a running difference image highlighting moving features is to be calculated by subtracting a previous image from the current one (or not): `-rd`

Retrieving the requested coronagraph images through the internet is done using the *Helioviewer.org* Application Programming Interface (API)¹⁹. The website [Helioviewer.org](https://helioviewer.org) provides JPEG2000 images to which all necessary calibration and background subtraction routines have already been applied and which include important metadata from the original FITS files. This speeds up the fitting process considerably compared to the IDL version, as neither a manual download of the FITS files nor locally applied calibration procedures are required. The default pixel count of the COR2 images is 2048×2048 pixels, and the default count of the C2 and C3 images is 1024×1024 pixels. The GCS mesh is applied to these images and the user can adjust the six GCS parameters with sliders. The times stamps of the downloaded images from C2/C3 and COR2 do not (and cannot) always match perfectly, as the coronagraphs have two different image cadences (see Section 4.5.1 and Section 4.5.2). After fitting, the resulting parameter values are stored in the JSON format, which is easy to handle for most modern programming languages.

5.2.2 In-Situ Solar Wind Data

The OMNIWeb Plus data service²⁰ provided by NASA is used in this work to acquire 1-min averaged WIND magnetic field and plasma data. This data is taken from an interface that is described on an associated website²¹. In the interface, a combination of the various solar wind parameters recorded by the instruments onboard the WIND spacecraft (see Section 4.4) can be selected. The graphic plots of the parameters are then output as an image for the desired period of time. For the best possible determination of in-situ ICME (and shock wave) arrival times, the following parameters are considered: the magnetic field strength B and its vector components B_x , B_y and B_z , as well as the flow speed, the proton density and the temperature of the plasma.

¹⁹Documentation: <https://api.helioviewer.org/docs/v2/> (last accessed September 2022)

²⁰OMNIWeb Plus website: <https://omniweb.gsfc.nasa.gov> (last accessed September 2022)

²¹About-website for the interface (last accessed September 2022):
https://omniweb.gsfc.nasa.gov/html/sc_merge_interface1.html

5.3 Data Analysis

5.3.1 Geometric CME Modelling with the GCS Model

In the Python implementation (see Section 5.2.1), the basic GCS geometry (see Section 3.3.1) is implemented as a close translation of the corresponding IDL routines from SolarSoft. Circles (with appropriate radii and orientations) are generated around the central axis of the GCS skeleton to create a 3D mesh. In order to adapt the mesh to the CME, the following parameters (introduced in Section 3.3.1) can be adjusted as desired in the GUI: the half angle α , the CME front height h_{apex} and the aspect ratio κ . Additionally, the model can be rotated in 3D space by providing the three angles ϕ , θ and γ also introduced in Section 3.3.1 (note Equation (3)). The following explains the process that was gone through to apply the GCS model to white light observations of CME clouds.

First, the short films provided for STEREO's coronagraphs on the website https://cdaw.gsfc.nasa.gov/stereo/daily_movies/ and for SOHO's coronagraphs on the website https://cdaw.gsfc.nasa.gov/CME_list/²² for the respective CME event were looked at more closely. These movies are composed of the observed coronagraph images and provide information about the evolution of the CME event. This allows for an initial insight into the size of the CME and how it spreads. In addition, the CME can be distinguished from other objects (such as coronal streamers or shock waves), which is essential for accurate modelling. Using a running difference image (see Section 5.2.1) can help with these problems similarly well, as non-moving objects (light sources in the image background) and long-lasting phenomena (coronal streamers) are removed from the image. In the case where several CMEs occur in quick succession or close to each other, the movies are particularly helpful as they can be used to identify exactly which CME is the one to be modelled. Moreover, C2 and C3 both have FOV that are of interest for modelling CMEs. Depending on the spread and evolution of a specific event, either C2 or C3 may be better combined with COR2 and this can be quickly detected using the movies.

To start the modelling process, the image to be modelled is called in the GCS GUI as

²²This CME catalog is generated and maintained at the CDAW Data Center by NASA and The Catholic University of America in cooperation with the Naval Research Laboratory. SOHO is a project of international cooperation between ESA and NASA.

Figure 15: The GCS model applied to the observations of event UC1-CME-4 recorded by COR2B near L5 and C2 at L1 at 16:54 (UT) on May 24th, 2010. The CME is a medium fast Halo with a nicely visible flux-rope like structure in the COR2B FOV. However, this structure is only recognisable to some extent in the C2 FOV. In the COR2A image, coronal streamer activity is also visible. The presented images are running difference images processed as described in Section 5.2.1.

described in Section 5.2.1. The GCS model is applied to the CME clouds simultaneously from the perspective of L1 and L5. For example, the two FOV for the observations of event UC1-CME-4 recorded by COR2B and C2 can be seen in the GCS GUI in Figure 15.

All parameters are independent of each other and are therefore free variables. Since for the further procedure in this work (see Section 5.3.2) the kinematics of the CMEs must be determined as accurately as possible via height-time-profiles, the GCS model was only applied to observations in which the CME front height measures at least $10 R_{\odot}$. [Thernisien et al. \(2009\)](#) presented a short step-by-step guide describing how to adjust the parameters to get a good match with the CME's white-light appearance: they suggest that the longitude ϕ , latitude θ and height h should be adjusted first while the parameter α is set to zero. Now the parameter κ can be set in such a way that the spatial extension of the CME is described as well as possible. Finally, α and γ are set, although small changes to the other parameters may be necessary. However, the

Figure 16: The GCS model applied to the observations of event UC1-CME-3 recorded by COR2A near L5 and C3 at L1 around 04:38 (UT) on November 2nd, 2021. The CME is a very fast and massive Halo with an extensive structure. A preceding shock wave, as well as a secondary, previous CME are visible. The presented images are running difference images processed as described in Section 5.2.1.

approach to modelling in this work differed from event to event, as particular features of individual CMEs or unusual peculiarities in the coronagraph images had a major impact on the perception of the events. In the following, peculiarities that occurred when applying the GCS model to observed images of the CMEs from Table 4 are described. Due to the selection of events according to Section 5.1, many of the events are Halo-CMEs. When considering Halos, the CME front points either towards the Earth or away from the Earth. Therefore, the flux rope-like structure of a typical Halo is particularly difficult to identify in some images taken from C2 or C3 (see Figure 15).

The GCS model is most applicable when ideal flux rope-like morphology is visible. Not all CMEs match this form perfectly and therefore the application of the GCS model is error-prone or even questionable in some cases, since the CME cloud cannot be reproduced nicely. However, many of the selected events present a flux rope-like morphology as seen in the FOV of COR2B in Figure 15 to which the GCS model can be applied well.

CMEs identified as particularly fast events via the short movies (or via the subsequent

speed determination (see Section 5.3.2)) such as UC1-CME-3 (see Figure 16) often have a very extensive structure and therefore require that the GCS model needs to be applied less flux rope-like and replicating more of a spherical expansion. In addition, they sometimes must be distinguished from the brightness enhancement of a shock front in the image that precedes the CME front.

Finally, the CMEs must also be distinguished from other solar phenomena such as coronal streamers. Especially when the events occurred during the solar maximum, the images often include intense streamer activity or secondary CMEs (see Figure 16).

The human subjectivity on the application of the GCS model is presented in Section 6.1. Regarding the event UC1-CME-11, a very small and narrow CME was modelled. The event originally represented a different CME, but there was an issue which could not be resolved resulting in a strong misinterpretation. The results emerging in connection with this event, as well as further calculations involving these results, should be evaluated with caution.

5.3.2 ICME Propagation Modelling

To analyse the kinematics of ICMEs in the inner heliosphere with a propagation model, all necessary input parameters of the model must be determined. In this work, both the DBM (see Section 3.3.2) and the MODBM (see Section 3.3.3) are used for propagation modelling. While a few input parameters differ between the models, both use the same 3D CME input parameters that can be determined using the results from the application of the GCS model. These 3D CME input parameters are determined first. Therefore, it is described below how the initial radial distance r_0 , the initial apex velocity v_{apex} , the initial, Earth-directed velocity v_{earth} , the cross-section A and the mass M of each CME are calculated.

All propagation modelling in this work starts from a CME apex height of at least $12 R_{\odot}$. [Vourlidas et al. \(2010\)](#) showed that the mass and energy properties of most CMEs reach a steady state above about $10 R_{\odot}$ and, as described in Section 3.3.2, $c_d = 1$ is a valid approximation shortly after $12 R_{\odot}$ for the dimensionless drag coefficient. The exact value of the initial radial distance r_0 corresponds exactly to the lowest CME apex height h_{apex} , which is greater than $12 R_{\odot}$, resulting from the GCS model applications. By applying the GCS model to the complete observation sequence of the coronagraphs,

Figure 17: Velocity determination plot for event UC1-CME-4. The GCS apex heights h_{apex} determined via 3D modelling with assumed errors are plotted against the CME propagation time t . A χ^2 fit of a linear function of the presented form is applied. The slope a yields the CME apex velocity v_{apex} .

the initial apex velocity v_{apex} at the initial radial distance r_0 can be calculated via height-time-profiles. Each sequence contains all observations (that [Helioviewer.org](https://helioviewer.org) provides on its website) in which the CME is visible in its entirety in at least one of the coronagraphs and with an apex height of at least $10 R_{\odot}$ (so that there are enough observations for an accurate velocity determination). The expansion of the CME cloud around $12 R_{\odot}$ is assumed to be self-similar (e.g., [Chen \(1996\)](#), [Cremades and Bothmer \(2004\)](#)). This means that for all further images in a sequence, both $\alpha(r) = \text{const.}$ and $\kappa(r) = \text{const.}$ apply. Since the orientation of the CME also remains the same, only the apex height h_{apex} is a free parameter for all further modelling with the GCS model after the first modelling described in Section 5.3.1. The determined apex heights from all applications of the GCS model in a sequence are plotted against the propagation time of the CMEs. Within the plot, the *SciPy*-library²³ and its function *optimize.curve_fit* are used to fit a linear function of the form $f(t) = a \times t + b$ to the data using the least squares method (for more details see Section 6.2). The slope a of this fit represents the determined initial apex velocity v_{apex} for the respective CME. An intercept b is needed to compensate for the initial acceleration phase up to the time of the first observation.

²³SciPy library introduction (last accessed September 2022):
<https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/tutorial/general.html>

Figure 18: Velocity determination plot for event UC1-CME-3. The GCS apex heights h_{apex} determined via 3D modelling with assumed errors are plotted against the CME propagation time t . A χ^2 fit of a linear function of the presented form is applied. The slope a yields the CME apex velocity v_{apex} .

As an example, Figure 17 and Figure 18 show the velocity determination plots for events UC1-CME-4 and UC1-CME-3, respectively.

The assumption of self-similar expansion also implies that the speed-distribution of the CME front is not homogeneous and thus that, e.g., the propagation velocity of the flanks of the tubular section is smaller than the one of the apex. In CME forecast, one is more interested in the initial, Earth-directed velocity v_{earth} than in the velocity in apex direction. Concerning Equation (7), this is then to be equated with the initial velocity v_0 which is used as input for the propagation models. This velocity can be derived from the ratio of the GCS model front height in Earth-direction h_{earth} and the CME apex height h_{apex} via

$$v_{\text{earth}} = h_{\text{earth}}/h_{\text{apex}} \cdot v_{\text{apex}}. \quad (16)$$

Since it is not trivial to derive h_{earth} for most GCS shapes, the value is determined graphically in this work. For this purpose, the CME apex height is set to $h_{\text{apex}} = 1$ AU and a Sun-Earth connection line is drawn into the 3D plot of the GCS models of all events studied. This step is carried out with a program that has not yet been published, in which the GCS model and the DBM were implemented in IDL by former

Figure 19: Determination of the EAR value for event UC1-CME-4. A Sun-Earth connection line (blue) is drawn into the 3D GCS model plot and is adjusted in length so that it exactly meets the front of the GCS model as presented in the image. The apex height (red) set to a height of 1 AU is also shown. For this event, the value determined for the EAR is $h_{\text{earth}}/h_{\text{apex}} = 0.91$.

members of the working group of Dr. Bothmer, and which is affectionately called the “DoomsDay Calculator (DDC)” by its creators. If the GCS model of the respective CME intersects the line, presented as a blue line in Figure 19, the relative proportion of the line in front of the intersection point (i.e. between the Sun and the intersection point) determines the $h_{\text{earth}}/h_{\text{apex}}$ ratio (or the Earth-directed height to apex-directed height ratio (EAR)). However, if the GCS model does not intersect the line at any point (see Figure 23 in Appendix A.2), the EAR is zero and as a result the velocity v_{earth} as well, and thus it is assumed that the corresponding ICME does not hit the Earth. This also means that the propagation of the corresponding event is not modelled with the DBM or the MODBM. GCS models of reconstructed events that very narrowly fail to intersect the line (again, see Figure 23 in Appendix A.2) and thus are predicted to pass close to Earth are considered in more detail. It is expected that no ICME signature will appear in the WIND spacecraft in-situ data for these events (which will be described in more detail later). Therefore, by analysing the in-situ data in comparison with the determination of events that narrowly miss the Earth, statements can be made about

the accuracy of the determination procedure of the CME orientation carried out in this work.

The cross-section A is calculated utilising Equation (9) introduced in Section 3.3.2. It increases with the radial distance of the CME from the Sun and the formula for A is included in the determination of Γ for the modelling with the DBM, and, for the modelling with the MODBM, it is included in the equation of motion to be solved numerically. Therefore, the cross-section is not determined specifically, but indirectly within these procedures.

The mass M of each CME is determined via the empirical correlation introduced in Section 3.3.2. This means that the mass is calculated directly and exclusively via the velocity v_{apex} of the respective CME (see Equation (10)).

In the following, both the determination of the remaining, model-specific input parameters and the execution of the modelling for the two models are described.

Propagation modelling with the DBM

With the assumptions introduced in Section 3.3.2, the drag parameter γ is a constant input parameter for the DBM. It is calculated according to Equation (8) and then substituted with Γ via Equation (13). The calculations of the cross-section A and the mass M already described are part of the determination of γ . Furthermore, the approximation $c_d = 1$ is used for the dimensionless drag coefficient c_d , since the propagation modelling only starts from a CME apex height of at least $12 R_{\odot}$. Finally, the ambient solar wind density (see Equation (11)) is included, for which the particle density is modelled according to the approximation in Equation (12). It is very important to note that for a concrete calculation of γ the value of the cross-section $A(r)$ has to be determined in relation to the same radial distance r as the value of the ambient solar wind density $\rho_w(r)$. This follows from the fact that the quadratic dependence on r in the formula of $A(r)$ and the inverse quadratic dependence on r in the formula of $\rho_w(r)$ cancel each other out. As mentioned in Section 3.3.2, statistically derived values of Γ are in a range of $\Gamma = 0.1 - 2 \text{ km}^{-1}$ for magnetic ejecta.

The (constant) ambient solar wind speed w is the last input parameter of the DBM to be determined. With the help of the measurements of the WIND spacecraft (see Section 4.4), incoming ICMEs and associated interplanetary shocks, as well as the speed

Figure 20: In situ solar wind data recorded with the WIND spacecraft between November 3rd and November 7th, 2021. Starting with the top row and moving down the image, the magnetic field strength as a scalar quantity, the B_x , B_y and B_z components of the magnetic field strength, the flow speed, the proton density and the temperature are presented. A shock signature is first identified on 11/03 at approximately 20:20 (UT), while a ICME signature is first identified on 11/04 at 09:00 (UT).

of the solar wind preceding the ICME can be detected. Shocks are usually characterised in the data by a sharp, temporally short increase in all relevant solar wind plasma parameters. These include the magnetic field strength, the flow speed, the proton density and the temperature of the plasma. The shock is sometimes followed by the ICME, provided it also hits the WIND spacecraft. The ICME is usually represented by longer disturbance of the solar wind plasma parameters, compared to the shock disturbance. In Figure 20, this behaviour can be observed for event UC1-CME-3. The speed of the solar wind surrounding the ICME can be extracted from the data accurately (by taking the solar wind speed shortly before the arrival of the ICME or its associated shock) if the ICME being modelled hits the WIND spacecraft and its signature is clearly visible in the data. However, if no signature is clearly visible, the ambient solar wind speed is determined from data recorded at approximately the same time as the ICME

is expected to arrive at 1 AU (based on the travel time of other ICMEs analysed in this work with similar conditions).

The calculated input parameters of the DBM are used to determine the propagation

Figure 21: Comparison of the modelled 1D Earth-directed CME front propagations with the DBM and the MODBM for event UC1-CME-4. On the left hand side, the Earth-directed front height r is plotted against the time of propagation, while on the right hand side the ICME velocity v is plotted against the time of propagation t . Within the plots, dashed lines indicate at which point the Earth is reached. For this event, the resulting arrival times at 1 AU differ by about three hours.

of the modelled CME in the heliosphere and finally to “predict” the ICME arrival time at 1 AU. The analytical solution of the equation of motion (see Equation (7)) enables these steps to be carried out in a compact form. In a Python 3 environment, the analytical solution is set up as a function that takes all relevant parameters as input. It outputs the calculated Earth-directed ICME front height $r(t)$ for an elapsed propagation time t . The time derivative is considered for the determination of the ICME velocities. In addition, the 1D expansion of the front and the different ICME velocities along the propagation path are plotted graphically from the initial distance r_0 to 1 AU against the propagation time t utilising the *Matplotlib*²⁴ library (see Figure 21 and Figure 22). The plots can also be used to compare the two models, since the 1D expansion and the velocities determined with the MODBM are also entered in the plots. Of greatest interest are the determined arrival times at 1 AU, which can be compared (see Section 6.3) not only with the arrival times of the other model, but also with the in-situ data of the WIND spacecraft, if a ICME signature was measured.

²⁴Matplotlib library homepage: <https://matplotlib.org> (last accessed September 2022)

Figure 22: Comparison of the modelled 1D Earth-directed CME front propagations with the DBM and the MODBM for event UC1-CME-3. On the left hand side, the Earth-directed front height r is plotted against the time of propagation, while on the right hand side the ICME velocity v is plotted against the time of propagation t . Within the plots, dashed lines indicate at which point the Earth is reached. For this event, the resulting arrival times at 1 AU only differ by about half an hour.

Propagation modelling with the MODBM

The additional input parameters for the MODBM described in the following are the SSN at the time of occurrence of the respective event and the information whether the ICME propagates in a fast solar wind dominated environment or in a slow solar wind dominated environment. The SSN is inserted into Equation (15) to allow the calculation with a proton density relation that is more consistent with recent scientific findings by [Venzmer and Bothmer \(2018\)](#). The SSN is entered into the MODBM in the form of the 13-month smoothed monthly total sunspot number. This number is provided by the Royal Observatory of Belgium as SILSO data from 1749 until now²⁵. The type of solar wind environment can be determined indirectly via the ambient solar wind speed w , which has already been calculated for modelling with the DBM. Since the solar wind speeds of the two model types (see Equation (14)) assume very different values at a radial distance of 1 AU (363 km s^{-1} for the slow solar wind and 483 km s^{-1} for the fast solar wind), the previously measured speed w is often much closer to one of these values, which then determines the type. If the measured data shows a transition between the two solar wind types, the type closer in time to the estimated or measured arrival time of the ICME is chosen.

²⁵SSN data (new version): <https://www.sidc.be/silso/newdataset> (last accessed September 2022)

The programming effort associated with the implementation of MODBM is significantly greater than that of DBM, since the equation of motion must now be solved numerically as a homogeneous linear second-order ordinary differential equation (ODE) initial value problem. First, the homogeneous linear second-order ODE that is Equation (6) is converted into a system of two homogeneous linear first-order differential equations: by defining two new, unknown functions $r_1 = r$ and $r_2 = \frac{dr}{dt}$, the 2D system of first-order coupled ODEs is then

$$\frac{dr_1}{dt} = r_2 \quad (17)$$

$$\frac{dr_2}{dt} = -\gamma(r_1) \left(\frac{dr_1}{dt} - w(r_1) \right) \left| \frac{dr_1}{dt} - w(r_1) \right| \quad (18)$$

$$\text{with } \gamma(r_1) = -\frac{c_d}{M} \cdot \left(\frac{r_1}{1 + \kappa} \right)^2 \pi \tan(\alpha) \tan(\arcsin(\kappa))$$

$$\cdot m_p \cdot (0.0038 [\text{cm}^{-3}] \cdot SSN + 4.50 [\text{cm}^{-3}]) \cdot r_1^{-2.11}$$

$$\text{and } w(r_1) = w_0 \cdot r_1^{0.099} \quad \text{with } w_0 = \begin{cases} 363 \text{ km s}^{-1}, & \text{for slow ambient solar wind.} \\ 483 \text{ km s}^{-1}, & \text{for fast ambient solar wind.} \end{cases}$$

The relevant equations from Section 3.3.2 and Section 3.3.3 are already used here, namely Equation (9), Equation (11), Equation (14) and Equation (15). The variables are described in more detail in the chapters from which the equations originate. Next, the system consisting of Equation (17) and Equation (18) is integrated using the *scipy.integrate.odeint* function (again from the *SciPy* library) with defined initial values r_0 and v_{earth} which differ for each event. While more integration steps (or smaller time steps in the integration by the *scipy.integrate.odeint* function) improve the accuracy by a few minutes in the arrival time at 1 AU, the computational effort also increases. The output is similar to the output of the DBM. A plot of the 1D expansion of the ICME front $r(t)$ and the ICME velocity $v(t)$ from the initial height r_0 to 1 AU (see Figure 21 and Figure 22) and, most importantly, the ICME arrival time at 1 AU is returned. Again, this arrival time can then be compared to the result obtained with the DBM and the in-situ measurements.

6 Results and Discussion

In this chapter, the results obtained with the procedures/methods described in the previous chapter are presented and explained. Furthermore, relevant sources of error and particularities of the methods are described and discussed with regard to their influence. The results are also put into context with the work.

6.1 3D Modelling with the GCS Model

Each CME from Table 4 was reconstructed using the GCS modelling technique. The results of the CME modelling are presented in Table 5. The table contains the GCS parameters determined for a specific observation indicated in the “Time Stamp” column. As described in Section 5.3.2, the CMEs were also reconstructed in every image (provided by Helioviewer.org) of the complete observation sequence of the coronagraphs, in which the determined GCS apex height measured at least $10 R_{\odot}$. Following the assumption of self-similar expansion, only the apex heights were adjusted. The reconstructed apex heights of all the observations analysed, accompanied by the time stamps of the respective images, are listed in Table 10 in Appendix A.1.

When discussing these results, it should first be mentioned that the determination of the GCS parameters depends to a certain extent on the modeller and their interpretation of the CME structure in the respective image, which is why modelling with the GCS model is subjective to a certain extent. It also requires a certain amount of experience and skill in handling and adjusting the parameters in order to achieve an optimal match with the white-light appearance of the CME (Thernisien et al., 2009). Thus, the parameters determined in this work will (most likely) differ from those determined by an experienced modeller for the same events. Thernisien et al. (2009) performed a sensitivity analysis to estimate errors associated with this modelling method. Recently, Verbeke et al. (2022) studied “how subjectivity affects the 3D CME parameters that are obtained from the GCS reconstruction technique” (Verbeke et al., 2022) and determined the following error bars for quantifying the minimum error of CME parameters obtained from white-light reconstructions: $\Delta\phi = 11^{\circ}_{-6^{\circ}}^{+18^{\circ}}$, $\Delta\theta = 6^{\circ}_{-3^{\circ}}^{+2^{\circ}}$, $\Delta\gamma = 25^{\circ}_{-7^{\circ}}^{+8^{\circ}}$, $\Delta\alpha = 10^{\circ}_{-6^{\circ}}^{+12^{\circ}}$, $\Delta h = 0.6_{-0.4}^{+1.2} R_{\odot}$ and $\Delta\kappa = 0.1_{-0.02}^{+0.03}$. These error bars are in good agreement with the “wobble room” that arises in the modelling process performed in this work. The

Table 5: Results of the geometric CME modelling with the GCS model. The values of the parameters ϕ (Stonyhurst longitude), θ (latitude), γ (tilt), h_{apex} (apex height), κ (aspect ratio) and α (half angle) of the applied model are shown. The time stamp of the COR2 and C2/C3 observations, at which the respective CME was modelled, is also entered.

CME-ID	Time Stamp (UT) y/m/d:hm	ϕ [deg]	θ [deg]	γ [deg]	h_{apex} R_{\odot}	κ –	α [deg]
UC1-CME-1	2010/04/08:0639	19	–8	9	12.1	0.26	11
UC1-CME-2	2020/10/26:2224	214	6	8	12.2	0.23	16
UC1-CME-3	2021/11/02:0423	358	22	–78	15.3	0.73	38
UC1-CME-4	2010/05/24:1724	19	–3	–43	12.6	0.34	24
UC1-CME-5	2009/12/16:0654	357	8	–9	12.1	0.33	35
UC1-CME-6	2011/06/14:1054	326	0	66	12.3	0.41	31
UC1-CME-7	2010/03/19:1854	43	–8	5	12.9	0.34	19
UC1-CME-8	2010/04/03:1154	9	–23	13	12.7	0.42	18
UC1-CME-9	2021/10/28:1653	359	–26	–3	12.9	0.78	55
UC1-CME-10	2020/12/07:1742	12	–29	–73	13.0	0.79	50
UC1-CME-11	2020/09/04:0126	338	6	3	12.2	0.04	5
UC1-CME-12	2021/02/10:2324	29	–4	89	12.3	0.21	15
UC1-CME-13	2011/05/25:0154	128	29	75	15.4	0.35	23
UC1-CME-14	2011/07/11:1439	346	–8	22	12.1	0.15	17
UC1-CME-15	2011/10/29:0024	152	–28	–65	13.2	0.18	9

“wobble room” represents the fact that for most models, despite slight adjustments of the parameters, a good agreement of the model with the white-light signatures of the CMEs is still achieved. However, in the context of this work, these subjective effects are not studied in sufficient detail to allow the determination of concrete error bars. It should be noted that the values of the GCS parameters in Table 5 are rounded according to the error bars listed above.

In addition to the certain degree of subjectivity involved in the modelling and the aforementioned error bars of the parameters, the particularities of the individual events and circumstances of the observations/images also influence the accuracy of the reconstruction. In the following, the particular influences that have become noticeable in the modelling process and that have already been described in Section 5.3.1 are therefore assessed in terms of their severity. Due to the subjective nature of these influences, it is impossible to specify a concrete error size. Therefore, within the framework of a subjective opinion, the influences are ranked according to their expected severity:

1. **Halo-CMEs/disk events in C2 and C3:** The flux rope-like structures of

some Halos/disk events in this particular data set were difficult to identify or not visible at all in the images taken by C2 and C3. For events UC1-CME-2 and -4, the CME structures were only recognisable to some extent. However, for event UC1-CME-14, the structure in the FOV of C2 and C3 was nearly unidentifiable, and therefore the reconstruction relied heavily on the images taken by COR2.

2. **Narrow CMEs:** [Chen \(2011\)](#) describes a fundamental difference between narrow and normal CMEs, as narrow CMEs tend to show jet-like motions and no clear frontal loop. When modelling the events UC1-CME-11, -14 and -15, exactly this behaviour can be observed: no clear flux rope-like structure can be identified, which is why the application of the GCS model seems questionable in these cases and larger error margins concerning the determined parameters are to be expected.
3. **Fast CMEs:** The extensive, less flux rope-like structure of fast CME events like UC1-CME-3, -9 and -10 requires the GCS model to be adapted accordingly, which is often more difficult. In particular, the adjustment of the GCS parameters α and κ is more difficult, since a larger “wobble room” is created in which different combinations of these two parameters lead to a good agreement between the model and the white-light signatures.
4. **Coronal streamers, shock waves and secondary CMEs:** Each CME must be distinguished from other solar phenomena present in the image and preceding shock waves. Especially for events that are not clearly visible in the FOV of one of the coronagraphs, a presence of well-visible other solar phenomena leads to the fact that modelling has to be done with great caution. Some events occur together with (several) other CMEs in rapid succession and a first identification of the CMEs to be modelled was not clear for all events. However, in this data set, the vast majority of events can be clearly distinguished from other phenomena.

Although the implementation of the GCS model in Python is error-free ([Freiherr von Forstner, 2020](#), sec. B.3), subjective errors must be assigned to all determined GCS model parameters. A detailed determination is not made, as it would greatly extend the scope of this work.

Overall, the 3D modelling of all 15 events was successfully performed using the GCS model. These results can be used as a reference point for further modelling and

calculations, such as propagation modelling. Furthermore, it is already apparent from the influences on the modelling and in particular their weighting that this type of determination has clear advantages over modelling that is only carried out using data from the L1 viewpoint. For example, projection effects, which are especially relevant when Halos are analysed as disk events from only one viewpoint (Burkepile et al., 2004), do not affect the second viewpoint in the same way. In addition, poorly identifiable flux rope-like structures of Halos can be captured much better from the L5 viewpoint. Moreover, other solar phenomena influencing the modelling can be better captured and included/corrected. The overestimation of CME widths and the underestimation of CME speeds (e.g., Burkepile et al. 2004), which often occur in connection with single-viewpoint observations, can also be corrected.

Determination of the EAR values

The GCS model was then reproduced in the “DoomsDay Calculator” to determine the ratio $h_{\text{earth}}/h_{\text{apex}}$ referred to as EAR for use in Equation (16). The determined values of EAR are entered in Table 6. The systematic error arising from this graphical determination is set to $\sigma_{\text{EAR}} = 0.01$ due to the high clarity and accuracy of the program. Since this error is assumed to be the same for all events in the graphical determination, it is not entered in Table 6. In cases where a value of $\text{EAR} = 0$ was determined, however, an error of $\sigma_{\text{EAR}} = 0$ is assumed, as these cases can be clearly distinguished as borderline cases due to the mentioned clarity of the programme.

Analysis of the events that narrowly miss the Earth

In this way, events that narrowly miss the Earth (marked with [NM] in table Table 6) were also identified as such. The near miss events, UC1-CME-6, -7 and -12, are compared to the ICME signatures identified in the solar wind data and entered in Table 8. For events UC1-CME-7 and -12 no such signature is recognisable in the data. However, it can be identified for UC1-CME-6. Thus, two of the three events were correctly predicted to miss the Earth.

Discussing these results, it should be noted that no general statement can be made about the accuracy of the determination of the CME orientation with the GCS model from the L1 and L5 viewpoints. The sample size of CMEs that just miss the Earth

included in the data selection is too small. This also means that the influence of certain event-specific errors, which were discussed in more detail at the beginning of this chapter, cannot be assessed and there is a risk that the results will be strongly influenced by one of these effects.

6.2 Determination of Propagation Model Input Parameters

Calculation of the apex-directed and Earth-directed velocity and the mass

The via height-time-profiles and fitting of a linear function determined CME apex velocities are entered in Table 6 together with the systematic errors arising from this type of determination. The determination of these errors is described in more detail below. It should be noted that, in addition to the systematic errors, the subjective errors mentioned in the last chapter also have an influence on the velocity determination, as it is carried out directly from the GCS parameters previously determined. For all

Table 6: Results of the determination of necessary input parameters used by both propagation models in this work. The propagation modelling start time, the initial Earth-directed CME velocity v_{earth} (at the starting height r_0), and the mass M are entered for all events. Two quantities that play a role in the determination of these parameters, namely the apex-directed velocity v_{apex} and the EAR, are also listed. The events that are expected to narrowly miss the Earth are marked with [NM].

CME-ID	Start Time (UT) y/m/d:hm	r_0 R_{\odot}	v_{apex} km s^{-1}	EAR	v_{earth} km s^{-1}	M 10^{15} g
UC1-CME-1	2010/04/08:0639	12.1	430 ± 40	0.83	357 ± 40	4.21
UC1-CME-2	2020/10/26:2224	12.2	327 ± 16	0	0	3.89
UC1-CME-3	2021/11/02:0353	12.7	1220 ± 80	0.96	1171 ± 80	7.85
UC1-CME-4	2010/05/24:1724	12.6	666 ± 23	0.91	606 ± 23	5.07
UC1-CME-5	2009/12/16:0654	12.1	480 ± 40	0.97	467 ± 40	4.38
UC1-CME-6	2011/06/14:1054	12.3	735 ± 7	0 [NM]	0	5.36
UC1-CME-7	2010/03/19:1854	12.9	339 ± 13	0 [NM]	0	3.93
UC1-CME-8	2010/04/03:1154	12.7	860 ± 13	0.69	593 ± 13	5.91
UC1-CME-9	2021/10/28:1653	12.9	1650 ± 50	0.87	1436 ± 50	10.94
UC1-CME-10	2020/12/07:1742	13.0	1350 ± 70	0.92	1243 ± 70	8.67
UC1-CME-11	2020/09/04:0126	12.2	257 ± 14	0	0	3.68
UC1-CME-12	2021/02/10:2324	12.3	190 ± 50	0 [NM]	0	3.49
UC1-CME-13	2011/05/25:0154	15.4	567 ± 16	0	0	4.70
UC1-CME-14	2011/07/11:1439	12.1	529 ± 8	0.93	491 ± 8	4.56
UC1-CME-15	2011/10/29:0024	13.2	486 ± 11	0	0	4.41

determined GCS apex heights an approximate maximum error of $\sigma_{h_{\text{apex}}} = 0.5 R_{\odot}$ is

assumed. The fit performed is a χ^2 fit, thus χ^2 is minimised. χ^2 is defined as

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{N_t} \frac{(h_{\text{apex},i} - f(t_i))^2}{\sigma_{h_{\text{apex}}}^2} \quad (19)$$

where N_t is the number of modelled observations. Moreover, $f(t_i)$ is the value of the fit function at the time of the observation at which the height $h_{\text{apex},i}$ was obtained. Since there is only one degree of freedom, χ^2 can be used directly to evaluate the quality of the fit.

The χ^2 values for the velocity determinations performed in this work range between $0.14 < \chi^2 < 1.08$. Thus, the assumed error of $\sigma_{h_{\text{apex}}} = 0.5 R_{\odot}$ for the apex height determination is too large for most events, as the values agree better with the applied linear fit than the error suggest. This also indicates that the assumption of a constant CME velocity near the Sun is well reflected in the data for all events and that the reconstruction of apex heights with the GCS model can be well combined with a velocity determination by applying a linear fit.

It should be noted that the data provided by Helioviewer.org is partly incomplete and not all images could be analysed according to the cadence of the coronagraphs. The resulting data gaps naturally prevent the highest possible accuracy from being achieved in determining the velocity based on the satellite data. However, since a good fit with respect to the assumed errors could always be achieved even with these data gaps, thus, this potential influence can be considered rather small.

The Earth-directed velocities calculated via Equation (16) are also entered in Table 6 accompanied by the systematic errors resulting from the chosen method of determination. Since both, the values of the EAR and the apex-directed velocities v_{apex} , are provided with errors, these errors propagate via

$$\sigma_{v_{\text{earth}}} = \sqrt{(v_{\text{apex}} \cdot \sigma_{\text{EAR}})^2 + (\text{EAR} \cdot \sigma_{v_{\text{apex}}})^2} \quad (20)$$

into Equation (16) according to the principle of Gaussian error propagation. $\sigma_{v_{\text{apex}}}$ indicates the errors provided for the apex velocities, while σ_{EAR} represents the errors assumed for the determination of the EAR. Here too, the subjective errors mentioned in the last chapter propagate into this velocity determination and can therefore influence its results.

The determined CME masses are entered in Table 6 without associated error. This is because the empirical correlation according to Equation (10), which is used in this work for the mass determination, is already strongly dependent on the conditions chosen by [Pluta et al. \(2018\)](#) for the development of the correlation (also see [Pluta 2018](#)). Furthermore, the determination is also influenced by the subjective errors discussed earlier and other systematic errors resulting from the propagation of the errors of the Earth-directed velocities in Equation (10) according to the Gaussian error propagation. A more detailed error investigation is needed to analyse how these errors propagate, but this exceeds the scope of this work.

When discussing the mass calculations, it should be noted that the empirical nature of the correlation used inevitably leads to the CME masses taking on unrealistic values when determined for extraordinary CME events. Since the correlation links the mass directly and exclusively with the apex velocity, for event UC1-CME-11, a similar mass is determined as for event UC1-CME-2, for example, although the parameters of their spatial expansion, κ and α , (and thus very likely also their actual masses) differ substantially (see Table 5). Mass determination using the white-light signatures of the CMEs in the coronagraph images would possibly contribute to a significantly higher accuracy. [Pluta et al. \(2018\)](#) presented a combined geometrical modelling and white-light mass determination using the GCS model which could be applied in this step.

Determination of the drag parameter

The results of the drag parameter determination via Equation (8) and Equation (13) are entered in Table 7. No corresponding errors are indicated in the table. According to Gaussian error propagation, the errors of the mass and the cross-section need to be included in a consideration of the systematic errors of this determination. A detailed error analysis therefore again exceeds the scope of this work, but it can be stated that the subjective errors of the GCS modelling also are of relevance here. These are not only included via the CME mass M , as described above, but also via the cross-section A . In the calculation, which makes use of Equation (9) and thus of the GCS parameters κ and α , these errors also enter. Originally, the (exact) value for the cross-section is determined numerically as described by [Thernisien \(2011\)](#). The inaccuracy resulting

Table 7: Results of the determination of model-specific input parameters of the two propagation models used in this work. As input for the DBM, the drag parameter Γ and the constant ambient solar wind velocity w are entered for events that are predicted to hit the Earth. As input for the MODBM, the determined type of solar wind environment according to Equation (14) is entered. Again, the start time of the propagation modelling and the starting height r_0 are presented.

CME-ID	Start Time (UT) y/m/d:hm	r_0 R_\odot	Γ km^{-1}	w km s^{-1}	$w_{\text{med}}^{\text{slow}}$ or $w_{\text{med}}^{\text{fast}}$
UC1-CME-1	2010/04/08:0639	12.1	0.06	370	w^{slow}
UC1-CME-3	2021/11/02:0353	12.7	0.29	500	w^{fast}
UC1-CME-4	2010/05/24:1724	12.6	0.15	320	w^{slow}
UC1-CME-5	2009/12/16:0654	12.1	0.25	390	w^{slow}
UC1-CME-8	2010/04/03:1154	12.7	0.11	525	w^{fast}
UC1-CME-9	2021/10/28:1653	12.9	0.42	325	w^{slow}
UC1-CME-10	2020/12/07:1742	13.0	0.45	355	w^{slow}
UC1-CME-14	2011/07/11:1439	12.1	0.06	490	w^{fast}

from the approximation and analytical determination is assumed to be negligible. Only two events fall outside the statistically derived, expected range of $\Gamma = 0.1 - 2 \text{ km}^{-1}$ (Vršnak et al., 2013) by a small margin. This can be regarded as a small “sanity check”; the determined values can be used as input for the DBM as intended by Vršnak et al. (2013).

Extraction of the ambient solar wind speed and environment type

The ambient solar wind speed as the last, necessary input parameter of the DBM, is entered in Table 7. An error of $\sigma_w = 15 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ is assumed for the extraction of all values for w from the in-situ data. For events, for which no in-situ signatures could be identified, the inaccuracy may be much greater, but no exact value can be approximated. In addition to this error, there are effects that influence the propagation of ICMEs in the ambient solar wind, but cannot be included in the prediction via the DBM (or the MODBM). First of all, the solar wind can change its speed within a short time period. Therefore, a single value does not always reflect the speed of the solar wind, which is most relevant for the ICME acceleration. The spatial extent of the ICMEs, which can also propagate in different ambient solar wind currents of differing speeds (Temmer et al., 2011), is not considered in the models. Furthermore, the interactions between shocks and the solar wind (Molotkov and Atamaniuk, 2020), which can influence the propagation of the ICMEs behind them, cannot be considered either.

The resulting ambient solar wind types determined together with the ambient solar wind speeds can also be found in Table 7. It is possible to decide clearly between the type of solar wind environment for all events considered in this work, so that no inaccuracy occurs. However, this would change in the case where an ICME arrives near a transition between the two solar wind types. The inclusion of this case is not yet implemented in the MODBM. The above-mentioned potential shortcomings of the DBM in relation to effects associated with the solar wind may also have an impact on the results of the MODBM.

In summary, all parameters that represent the necessary input for both the DBM and the MODBM have been successfully determined. The sources of error listed for each of the parameters propagate partially through several formulas and determinations. The subjective errors that originate from the 3D reconstruction of the CMEs by applying the GCS model can also potentially have an influence on many of the input parameters, which is why a detailed analysis of the errors is beyond the scope of this work.

6.3 ICME Arrival Times

Table 8 lists the calculated ICME arrival times next to the actual arrival times determined from the in-situ solar wind data. In the case of UC1-CME-10, a shock signature could be identified in-situ, but no ICME signature. An error of 0.5 h is assumed for the extraction of the ICME arrival times from the WIND spacecraft data. A comparison of the arrival times calculated via propagation modelling and the actual arrival times, and a comparison of the propagation modelling results with each other is carried out in Table 9.

Before a first discussion of the results, it should be noted that the in-situ data was measured by the WIND spacecraft placed in L1, thus the arrival of all modelled ICMEs at L1 is about 1 hour earlier than the times shown in the tables (which represent the arrival time at Earth). However, this does not influence the following analysis of the results.

It quickly becomes clear that a large proportion of the results deviate greatly from the arrival times determined in-situ. This is also noticeable when considering the results that were only obtained using the DBM. For isolated events propagating in a “simple” solar wind environment, however, the expected typical prediction error for modelling

Table 8: Arrival time (AT) prediction results from the propagation modelling with the DBM and the MODBM together with the ICME arrival times measured in-situ at L1. The (potential) start time of the propagation modelling accompanies these results. The asterisk “*” indicates that instead of an ICME signature only a shock signature could be extracted. The hyphen “–” indicates that no signature was visible or that no modelling of the event was performed, depending on the column in which it is entered.

CME-ID	Start Time (UT) y/m/d:hm	AT _{in-situ} d:hm	AT _{DBM} d:hm	AT _{MODBM} d:hm
UC1-CME-1	2010/04/08:0639	12:0200	12:2040	12:2116
UC1-CME-2	2020/10/26:2224	–	–	–
UC1-CME-3	2021/11/02:0353	04:0900	04:0543	04:0607
UC1-CME-4	2010/05/24:1724	28:2000	27:2219	27:1907
UC1-CME-5	2009/12/16:0654	–	19:2303	20:0353
UC1-CME-6	2011/06/14:1054	17:0500	–	–
UC1-CME-7	2010/03/19:1854	–	–	–
UC1-CME-8	2010/04/03:1154	05:1230	06:0623	06:0820
UC1-CME-9	2021/10/28:1653	–	31:1223	31:0558
UC1-CME-10	2020/12/07:1742	10:0230*	10:1624	10:1113
UC1-CME-11	2020/09/04:0126	–	–	–
UC1-CME-12	2021/02/10:2324	–	–	–
UC1-CME-13	2011/05/25:0154	28:0154	–	–
UC1-CME-14	2011/07/11:1439	–	14:2230	14:2302
UC1-CME-15	2011/10/29:0024	–	–	–

with the DBM is 0.5 days (Vršnak et al., 2013). Although the sample size of modelled events is rather small, it can be assumed that large inaccuracies occur in the parameter determination. Within the framework of this work, it is not possible to examine this in greater depth, and therefore the events are not examined in detail for the influence of inaccuracies. The following two parameter determinations, which have been described in more detail in previous chapters, should be noted as relevant and potentially large sources of error: the determination of the mass and the subjectivity in the determination of the GCS parameters. These also influence the propagation modelling with both models in a comparable way. This explains the very small differences of about 0.5 h between the arrival times determined with both models, which are entered in the last column of the table Table 9. The larger differences of about 5.17 h that occur in the modelling of the events UC1-CME-5, -9 and -10 can, at first sight (compared to Table 7), be related to the determination of a (comparably) large value of the drag parameter Γ . An important difference between the models is that in the DBM a constant value for Γ is assumed along the entire propagation path, while this is not the case in the

Table 9: Arrival time (AT) prediction results from the propagation modelling with the DBM and the MODBM compared to each other and to the ICME arrival times measured in-situ at L1. The distances between the arrival times presented in Table 8 for the respective events are listed. The asterisk “*” indicates that the time difference is calculated in respect to a shock signature and not to an ICME signature.

CME-ID	$AT_{\text{DBM}} - AT_{\text{in-situ}}$ h:m	$AT_{\text{MODBM}} - AT_{\text{in-situ}}$ h:m	$AT_{\text{MODBM}} - AT_{\text{DBM}}$ h:m
UC1-CME-1	+18:40	+19:16	+00:36
UC1-CME-3	-03:17	-02:53	+00:24
UC1-CME-4	-21:41	-24:53	-03:12
UC1-CME-5	-	-	+04:50
UC1-CME-8	+17:53	+19:50	+01:57
UC1-CME-9	-	-	-05:25
UC1-CME-10	+13:54*	+08:43*	-05:11
UC1-CME-14	-	-	+00:32

MODBM. This can have an influence on these results in particular. A more detailed investigation of this circumstance is not carried out.

In conclusion, no statement can be made as to whether the MODBM has a higher accuracy in the propagation modelling of CMEs than the DBM and thus represents a potential improvement of the model. And to note the relevance of the inaccuracies in the parameter determination relative to the model differences: the difference between the results obtained with the two models is in all cases significantly smaller than the deviation of both models from the measured in-situ arrival time. UC1-CME-10 is excluded from this conclusion, as only one shock signature was measured and used for comparison, which in most cases arrives several hours before the ICME. In addition, the sample size is too small to allow quick conclusions about the major sources of error and how they affect the arrival time prediction.

7 Conclusion and Outlook

The 15 CMEs studied in this work were successfully reconstructed using the GCS modelling technique. The GCS model was applied to each (available) image of the complete observation sequence of coronagraphs for the respective event above a certain height. The various peculiarities and sources of error that occurred, some of which are subjective in nature, were described and classified according to their presumed influence. These results can be used as a reference point for further modelling and calculations. Significant advantages of modelling with two viewpoints at the same time compared to modelling only with data from the viewpoint of L1 were identified. The analysis of events that narrowly miss the Earth has not yielded a general statement about the accuracy of determining the CME orientation with the GCS model from the L1 and L5 perspectives.

The DBM was described and a modified version of it, which incorporates more recent scientific findings, the MODBM, was introduced. All parameters used as input for both the propagation models used were successfully determined. It was noted that the listed sources of error, such as systematic errors calculated via equations Equation (19) and Equation (20) or subjective errors resulting from the 3D reconstruction, propagate partially through several formulae and determinations and a deeper investigation would be needed to accurately determine these errors.

The arrival times of all events predicted to hit the Earth were forecasted by propagation modelling using the DBM and the MODBM. The results of the propagation modelling with both models were compared to each other and to ICME signatures identified in in-situ solar wind data. It was found that there were large inaccuracies in the determination of the parameters, but the results of the two models were oftentime very similar. No individual uncertainty factors could be identified as the sole cause for the deviations in the results. Moreover, no statement could be made as to whether the MODBM has a higher accuracy in forecasting the ICME arrival times of the studied events than the DBM.

To give an outlook, some questions and possibilities for further research on the topics of this thesis arise. First of all, the results of the 3D reconstruction of the selected events can be used to present a point of comparison with other methods of 3D reconstruction, and differences in accuracy between the models can be examined. Of greater interest,

however, is the extent to which results of a similar reconstruction, but with data of a different image resolution or cadence, differ from those presented in this work. This allows further analyses to be carried out directly in the sense of the mentioned UCs, which investigate various factors contributing to potential improvements in forecasting capabilities in preparation for the Vigil mission, and specifically in the sense of UC1. New questions arise, especially with regard to propagation modelling and the MODBM. Whether the MODBM more accurately predicts ICME arrival times than the DBM, for example, can be investigated by determining the input parameters of the models more precisely and by increasing the number of events studied, especially events that hit the Earth. The mass could be determined more precisely, for example, according to the method described by [Pluta et al. \(2018\)](#). They presented combined geometrical modelling and white-light mass determination, which could allow a much more precise determination of the mass than was possible in this work.

Lastly, the MODBM could also be compared with other propagation models. Newer modelling methods already achieve significantly smaller errors in the prediction of arrival times. Other DBM tools, such as the advanced 2D self-similar cone DBM or the 2D flattening cone DBM can present interesting points of comparison ([Dumbović et al., 2021](#)). Advances in prediction accuracy are also of great interest in the context of the preparation of the Vigil mission, as the fast and accurate prediction of arrival times is of great importance for our modern, high-tech society.

8 Bibliography

- Aschwanden, J. M. (1966). *Physics of the Solar Corona - An Introduction with Problems and Solutions*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin.
- Aulanier, G. (2013). *The physical mechanisms that initiate and drive solar eruptions*. Proceedings of the International Astronomical Union, 8(S300):184–196.
- Barnes, W. T., Bobra, M. G., Christe, S. D., Freij, N., Hayes, L. A., Ireland, J., Mumford, S., Perez-Suarez, D., Ryan, D. F., Shih, A. Y., Chanda, P., Glogowski, K., Hewett, R., Hughitt, V. K., Hill, A., Hiware, K., Inglis, A., Kirk, M. S. F., Konge, S., Mason, J. P., Maloney, S. A., Murray, S. A., Panda, A., Park, J., Pereira, T. M. D., Reardon, K., Savage, S., Sipőcz, B. M., Stansby, D., Jain, Y., Taylor, G., Yadav, T., Rajul, and Dang, T. K. (2020). *The SunPy Project: Open Source Development and Status of the Version 1.0 Core Package*. The Astrophysical Journal, 890(1):68.
- Biermann, L. (1951). *Kometenschweife und solare Korpuskularstrahlung*. Zeitschrift für Astrophysik, 29:274.
- Billings, D. E. (1966). *A guide to the solar corona*. Academic Press, New York.
- Bothmer, V. (2006). *The Solar Atmosphere and Space Weather*. Solar System Update, pages 1–53.
- Bothmer, V. and Zhukov, A. (2007). *The Sun as the prime source of space weather*. In Bothmer, V. and Daglis, I. A., editors, *Space Weather - Physics and Effects*, page 31. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg.
- Bougeret, J.-L., Kaiser, M. L., Kellogg, P. J., Manning, R., Goetz, K., Monson, S. J., Monge, N., Friel, L., Meetre, C. A., Perche, C., Sitruk, L., and Hoang, S. (1995). *WAVES: The radio and plasma wave investigation on the wind spacecraft*. Space Science Reviews, 71(1-4):231–263.
- Brueckner, G., Howard, R., Koomen, M., Korendyke, C., Michels, D., Moses, J., Socker, D., Dere, K., Lamy, P., Llebaria, A., Bout, M., Schwenn, R., Simnett, G., Bedford,

- D., and Eyles, C. (1995). *The large angle spectroscopic coronagraph (LASCO)*. Solar Physics, 162:357–402.
- Burkepile, J. T., Hundhausen, A. J., Stanger, A. L., St. Cyr, O. C., and Seiden, J. A. (2004). *Role of projection effects on solar coronal mass ejection properties: 1. A study of CMEs associated with limb activity*. Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics, 109(A3):A03103.
- Burlaga, L., Sittler, E., Mariani, F., and Schwenn, R. (1981). *Magnetic loop behind an interplanetary shock: Voyager, Helios, and IMP 8 observations*. Journal of Geophysical Research, 86(A8):6673–6684.
- Cane, H. V. and Richardson, I. G. (2003). *Interplanetary coronal mass ejections in the near-Earth solar wind during 1996–2002*. Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics, 108(A4).
- Cargill, P. J. (2004). *On the Aerodynamic Drag Force Acting on Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejections*. Solar Physics, 221(1):135–149.
- Carrington, R. C. (1859). *Description of a Singular Appearance seen in the Sun on September 1, 1859*. Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society, 20:13–15.
- Carroll, B. W. and Ostlie, D. A. (2006). *An introduction to modern astrophysics and cosmology*. Pearson.
- Chen, J. (1996). *Theory of prominence eruption and propagation: Interplanetary consequences*. Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics, 101(A12):27499–27519.
- Chen, P. F. (2011). *Coronal Mass Ejections: Models and Their Observational Basis*. Living Reviews in Solar Physics, 8(1):1.
- Colaninno, R. (2012). *Investigation of the Forces that Govern the Three-Dimensional Propagation and Expansion of Coronal Mass Ejections from Sun to Earth*. Ph.D. dissertation, George Mason University.
- Colaninno, R. C. and Vourlidas, A. (2009). *First Determination of the True Mass of Coronal Mass Ejections: A Novel Approach to Using the Two STEREO Viewpoints*. The Astrophysical Journal, 698(1):852–858.

- Connelly, J. N., Bizzarro, M., Krot, A. N., Nordlund, Å., Wielandt, D., and Ivanova, M. A. (2012). *The Absolute Chronology and Thermal Processing of Solids in the Solar Protoplanetary Disk*. *Science*, 338:651–655.
- Cremades, H. and Bothmer, V. (2004). *On the three-dimensional configuration of coronal mass ejections*. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 422:307.
- Domingo, V., Fleck, B., and Poland, A. I. (1995). *The SOHO Mission: an Overview*. *Solar Physics*, 162(1-2):1–37.
- Droege, W. and Schlickeiser, R. (1986). *Particle Acceleration in Solar Flares*. *Astrophysical Journal*, 305:909.
- Dumbović, M., Čalogović, J., Martinić, K., Vršnak, B., Sudar, D., Temmer, M., and Veronig, A. (2021). *Drag-Based Model (DBM) Tools for Forecast of Coronal Mass Ejection Arrival Time and Speed*. *Frontiers in Astronomy and Space Sciences*, 8.
- Forbes, T. G. (2000). *A review on the genesis of coronal mass ejections*. *Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics*, 105(A10):23153–23165.
- Freeland, S. L. and Handy, B. N. (1998). *Data Analysis with the SolarSoft System*. *Solar Physics*, 182(2):497–500.
- Freiherr von Forstner, J. L. (2020). *Multipoint observations of ICMEs in the inner heliosphere: Forbush decreases and remote sensing*. Ph.D. dissertation, Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel.
- Freiherr von Forstner, J. L., Dumbović, M., Möstl, C., Guo, J., Papaioannou, A., Elftmann, R., Xu, Z., Christoph Terasa, J., Kollhoff, A., Wimmer-Schweingruber, R. F., Rodríguez-Pacheco, J., Weiss, A. J., Hinterreiter, J., Amerstorfer, T., Bauer, M., Belov, A. V., Abunina, M. A., Horbury, T., Davies, E. E., O’Brien, H., Allen, R. C., Bruce, A. G., Berger, L., Boden, S., Cernuda Cargas, I., Eldrum, S., Espinosa Lara, F., Gómez Herrero, R., Hayes, J. R., Ho, G. C., Kulkarni, S. R., Jeffrey Lees, W., Martín, C., Mason, G. M., Pacheco, D., Prieto Mateo, M., Ravanbakhsh, A., Rodríguez Polo, O., Sánchez Prieto, S., Schlemm, C. E., Seifert, H., Tyagi, K., and Yedla, M. (2021). *Radial evolution of the April 2020 stealth coronal mass ejection*

- between 0.8 and 1 AU - Comparison of Forbush decreases at Solar Orbiter and near the Earth.* *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 656:A1.
- Garaud, P. (2020). *The Tachocline Revisited.* In *Astrophysics and Space Science Proceedings*, pages 207–220. Springer International Publishing.
- Gloeckler, G., Balsiger, H., Bürgi, A., Bochsler, P., Fisk, L. A., Galvin, A. B., Geiss, J., Gliem, F., Hamilton, D. C., Holzer, T. E., Hovestadt, D., Ipavich, F. M., Kirsch, E., Lundgren, R. A., Ogilvie, K. W., Sheldon, R. B., and Wilken, B. (1995). *The Solar Wind and Suprathermal Ion Composition Investigation on the Wind Spacecraft.* *Space Science Reviews*, 71(1-4):79–124.
- Howard, R. A., Michels, D. J., Sheeley, N. R., and Koomen, M. (1982). *The observation of a coronal transient directed at earth.* *The Astrophysical Journal*, 263.
- Howard, R. A., Moses, J. D., Vourlidas, A., Newmark, J. S., Socker, D. G., Plunkett, S. P., Korendyke, C. M., Cook, J. W., Hurley, A., Davila, J. M., Thompson, W. T., St Cyr, O. C., Mentzell, E., Mehalick, K., Lemen, J. R., Wuelser, J. P., Duncan, D. W., Tarbell, T. D., Wolfson, C. J., Moore, A., Harrison, R. A., Waltham, N. R., Lang, J., Davis, C. J., Eyles, C. J., Mapson-Menard, H., Simnett, G. M., Halain, J. P., Defise, J. M., Mazy, E., Rochus, P., Mercier, R., Ravet, M. F., Delmotte, F., Auchere, F., Delaboudiniere, J. P., Bothmer, V., Deutsch, W., Wang, D., Rich, N., Cooper, S., Stephens, V., Maahs, G., Baugh, R., McMullin, D., and Carter, T. (2008). *Sun Earth Connection Coronal and Heliospheric Investigation (SECCHI).* *Space Science Reviews*, 136(1-4):67–115.
- Howard, T. A. and Tappin, S. J. (2009). *Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejections Observed in the Heliosphere: 3. Physical Implications.* *Space Science Reviews*, 147(1-2):89–110.
- Hundhausen, A. J., Sawyer, C. B., House, L., Illing, R. M., and Wagner, W. J. (1984). *Coronal mass ejections observed during the solar maximum mission: Latitude distribution and rate of occurrence.* *J. Geophys. Research*, 89:2639–2646.
- Jackson, J. D. (1975). *Classical electrodynamics.* New York: Wiley.
- Jin, M., Manchester, W. B., van der Holst, B., Sokolov, I., Tóth, G., Mullinix, R. E., Taktakishvili, A., Chulaki, A., and Gombosi, T. I. (2017). *Data-constrained Coronal*

- Mass Ejections in a Global Magnetohydrodynamics Model*. The Astrophysical Journal, 834(2):173.
- Kaiser, M. L., Kucera, T. A., Davila, J. M., St. Cyr, O. C., Guhathakurta, M., and Christian, E. (2008). *The STEREO Mission: An Introduction*. Space Science Reviews, 136(1-4):5–16.
- Kivelson, M. G. and Russell, C. T. (1995). *Introduction to Space Physics*. Cambridge University Press.
- Lavraud, B., Liu, Y., Segura, K., He, J., Qin, G., Temmer, M., Vial, J. C., Xiong, M., Davies, J. A., Rouillard, A. P., Pinto, R., Auchère, F., Harrison, R. A., Eyles, C., Gan, W., Lamy, P., Xia, L., Eastwood, J. P., Kong, L., Wang, J., Wimmer-Schweingruber, R. F., Zhang, S., Zong, Q., Soucek, J., An, J., Prech, L., Zhang, A., Rochus, P., Bothmer, V., Janvier, M., Maksimovic, M., Escoubet, C. P., Kilpua, E. K. J., Tappin, J., Vainio, R., Poedts, S., Dunlop, M. W., Savani, N., Gopalswamy, N., Bale, S. D., Li, G., Howard, T., DeForest, C., Webb, D., Lugaz, N., Fuselier, S. A., Dalmasse, K., Tallineau, J., Vranken, D., and Fernández, J. G. (2016). *A small mission concept to the Sun-Earth Lagrangian L5 point for innovative solar, heliospheric and space weather science*. Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics, 146:171–185.
- Leblanc, Y., Dulk, G. A., and Bougeret, J. L. (1998). *Tracing the Electron Density from the Corona to 1 au*. Solar Physics, 183:165–180.
- Low, B. C., Munro, R. H., and Fisher, R. R. (1982). *The initiation of a coronal transient*. Astrophysical Journal, 254:335–342.
- Lyot, B. (1939). *The study of the solar corona and prominences without eclipses (George Darwin Lecture, 1939)*. Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society, 99:580.
- Mays, M. L., Thompson, B. J., Jian, L. K., Colaninno, R. C., Odstrcil, D., Möstl, C., Temmer, M., Savani, N. P., Collinson, G., Taktakishvili, A., MacNeice, P. J., and Zheng, Y. (2015). PROPAGATION OF THE 2014 JANUARY 7 CME AND RESULTING GEOMAGNETIC NON-EVENT. The Astrophysical Journal, 812(2):145.
- Millward, G., Biesecker, D., Pizzo, V., and de Koning, C. A. (2013). *An operational*

- software tool for the analysis of coronagraph images: Determining CME parameters for input into the WSA-Enlil heliospheric model.* Space Weather, 11(2):57–68.
- Molotkov, I. and Atamaniuk, B. (2020). *Interaction of interplanetary shock wave with the solar wind.* Journal of Atmospheric and Solar-Terrestrial Physics, 207:105340.
- Möstl, C., Amerstorfer, T., Palmerio, E., Isavnin, A., Farrugia, C. J., Lowder, C., Winslow, R. M., Donnerer, J. M., Kilpua, E. K. J., and Boakes, P. D. (2018). *Forward Modeling of Coronal Mass Ejection Flux Ropes in the Inner Heliosphere with 3DCORE.* Space Weather, 16(3):216–229.
- Parker, E. N. (1958). *Dynamics of the Interplanetary Gas and Magnetic Fields.* Astrophysical Journal, 128:664.
- Pluta, A. (2018). *White-Light Mass Determination and Geometrical Modelling of Coronal Mass Ejections.* Ph.D. dissertation, Georg-August-Universität Göttingen.
- Pluta, A., Mrotzek, N., Vourlidis, A., Bothmer, V., and Savani, N. (2018). *Combined geometrical modelling and white-light mass determination of coronal mass ejections.* Astronomy & Astrophysics, 623.
- Richard, R. L., El-Alaoui, M., Ashour-Abdalla, M., and Walker, R. J. (2002). *Interplanetary magnetic field control of the entry of solar energetic particles into the magnetosphere.* Journal of Geophysical Research (Space Physics), 107(A8):1184.
- Schrijver, C. J., Kauristie, K., Aylward, A. D., Denardini, C. M., Gibson, S. E., Glover, A., Gopalswamy, N., Grande, M., Hapgood, M., Heynderickx, D., Jakowski, N., Kalegaev, V. V., Lapenta, G., Linker, J. A., Liu, S., Mandrini, C. H., Mann, I. R., Nagatsuma, T., Nandy, D., Obara, T., Paul O’Brien, T., Onsager, T., Opgenoorth, H. J., Terkildsen, M., Valladares, C. E., and Vilmer, N. (2015). *Understanding space weather to shield society: A global road map for 2015-2025 commissioned by COSPAR and ILWS.* Advances in Space Research, 55(12):2745–2807.
- Schwabe, H. (1844). *Sonnenbeobachtungen im Jahre 1843. Von Herrn Hofrath Schwabe in Dessau.* Astronomische Nachrichten, 21(15):233.

- Schwenn, R. (1990). *Large-Scale Structure of the Interplanetary Medium*. In Schwenn, R. and Marsch, E., editors, *Physics of the Inner Heliosphere I: Large-Scale Phenomena*, page 99. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg New York.
- Sheeley, N. R., Howard, R. A., Koomen, M., Michels, D. J., Schwenn, R., Mühlhäuser, K.-H., and Rosenbauer, H. (1985). *Coronal mass ejections and interplanetary shocks*. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 90:163–175.
- Stix, M. (2004). *The Sun : An Introduction*. Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg New York. Also *Astronomy and Astrophysics Library*.
- Temmer, M., Rollett, T., Möstl, C., Veronig, A. M., Vršnak, B., and Odrščil, D. (2011). *INFLUENCE OF THE AMBIENT SOLAR WIND FLOW ON THE PROPAGATION BEHAVIOR OF INTERPLANETARY CORONAL MASS EJECTIONS*. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 743(2):101.
- Thernisien, A. (2011). *Implementation of the Graduated Cylindrical Shell Model for the Three-dimensional Reconstruction of Coronal Mass Ejections*. *The Astrophysical Journal Supplement*, 194(2):33.
- Thernisien, A., Vourlidas, A., and Howard, R. (2009). *Forward modeling of coronal mass ejections using STEREO/SECCHI data*. *Solar Physics*, 256:111–130.
- Thernisien, A. F. R., Howard, R. A., and Vourlidas, A. (2006). *Modeling of Flux Rope Coronal Mass Ejections*. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 652(1):763–773.
- Thompson, W. T. (2006). *Coordinate systems for solar image data*. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 449(2):791–803.
- Tousey, R. (1973). *The solar corona*. In *Space Research Conference*, volume 2, pages 713–730.
- Venzmer, M. S. and Bothmer, V. (2018). *Solar-wind predictions for the Parker Solar Probe orbit*. *Astronomy and Astrophysics*, 611:A36.
- Verbeke, C., Leila Mays, M., Kay, C., Riley, P., Palmerio, E., Dumbović, M., Mierla, M., Scolini, C., Temmer, M., Paouris, E., Balmaceda, L. A., Cremades, H., and

- Hinterreiter, J. (2022). *Quantifying errors in 3D CME parameters derived from synthetic data using white-light reconstruction techniques*. Advances in Space Research.
- Verbeke, C., Mays, M. L., Temmer, M., Bingham, S., Steenburgh, R., Dumbović, M., Núñez, M., Jian, L. K., Hess, P., Wiegand, C., Taktakishvili, A., and Andries, J. (2019). *Benchmarking CME Arrival Time and Impact: Progress on Metadata, Metrics, and Events*. Space Weather, 17(1):6–26.
- von Rosenvinge, T. T., Barbier, L. M., Karsch, J., Liberman, R., Madden, M. P., Nolan, T., Reames, D. V., Ryan, L., Singh, S., Trexel, H., Winkert, G., Mason, G. M., Hamilton, D. C., and Walpole, P. (1995). *The Energetic Particles: Acceleration, Composition, and Transport (EPACT) investigation on the WIND spacecraft*. Space Science Reviews, 71(1-4):155–206.
- Vourlidas, A., Howard, R. A., Esfandiari, E., Patsourakos, S., Yashiro, S., and Michalek, G. (2010). *COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF CORONAL MASS EJECTION MASS AND ENERGY PROPERTIES OVER A FULL SOLAR CYCLE*. The Astrophysical Journal, 722:1522 – 1538.
- Vršnak, B., Žic, T., Vrbanec, D., Temmer, M., Rollett, T., Möstl, C., Veronig, A., Čalogović, J., Dumbović, M., Lulić, S., Moon, Y. J., and Shanmugaraju, A. (2013). *Propagation of Interplanetary Coronal Mass Ejections: The Drag-Based Model*. Solar Physics, 285(1-2):295–315.
- Webb, D. F. and Howard, R. A. (1994). *The solar cycle variation of coronal mass ejections and the solar wind mass flux*. Journal of Geophysical Research, 99(A3):4201–4220.
- Webb, D. F. and Hundhausen, A. J. (1987). *Activity Associated with the Solar Origin of Coronal Mass Ejections*. Solar Physics, 108(2):383–401.
- Wolf, R. (1856). *Mittheilungen über die Sonnenflecken I*. Astronomische Mitteilungen der Eidgenössischen Sternwarte Zurich, 1:3–13.
- Xue, X. H., Wang, C. B., and Dou, X. K. (2005). *An ice-cream cone model for coronal mass ejections*. Journal of Geophysical Research: Space Physics, 110(A8).

Zhao, X. and Dryer, M. (2014). *Current status of CME/shock arrival time prediction*.
Space Weather, 12(7):448–469.

A Appendix

A.1 Reconstructed Apex Heights and Corresponding Image Time Stamps Used in Velocity Determination

[The table is displayed on the following page.]

Table 10: The reconstructed GCS apex heights for the observations analysed in this work, accompanied by the time stamps of the respective images taken by COR2 and C2/C3. The other five parameters of the applied GCS models can be found in Table 5 for the respective event. The times are given in universal time (UT).

CME-ID UC1-...	Date y/m/d	h_{apex}											
		Time h:m	R_{\odot}										
CME-1	2010/04/08	06:39	12.1	06:54	13.0	07:24	13.9	07:54	15.0	—	—	—	—
CME-2	2020/10/26	21:54	11.2	22:24	12.2	22:39	12.7	22:54	13.0	23:24	13.8	—	—
CME-3	2021/11/02	03:53	12.7	04:23	15.3	04:38	17.2	04:53	19.0	—	—	—	—
CME-4	2010/05/24	16:54	10.89	17:24	12.56	17:39	13.3	17:54	14.1	18:24	16.1	—	—
CME-5	2009/12/16	06:54	12.1	07:24	13.0	07:39	13.4	07:54	14.3	08:24	15.8	—	—
CME-6	2011/06/14	10:39	11.3	10:54	12.3	11:09	13.2	11:24	14.2	11:39	15.1	11:54	17.0
CME-7	2010/03/19	18:54	12.9	19:24	14.1	19:54	14.8	20:24	15.7	20:54	16.4	21:24	—
CME-8	2010/04/03	11:24	10.6	11:39	11.6	11:54	12.7	12:24	14.9	12:39	16.1	—	—
CME-9	2021/10/28	16:42	11.7	16:53	12.9	17:18	16.3	17:30	18.3	17:54	21.8	—	—
CME-10	2020/12/07	17:30	11.7	17:42	13.0	17:54	14.3	18:18	16.8	18:30	18.9	—	—
CME-11	2020/09/04	00:48	11.3	01:26	12.2	01:36	12.6	02:00	13.0	02:24	13.4	—	—
CME-12	2021/02/10	23:24	12.3	23:39	12.8	23:54	13.1	00:24	13.3	—	—	—	—
CME-13	2011/05/25	01:54	15.4	02:09	16.1	02:24	17.0	02:39	17.8	02:54	18.4	03:24	19.8
CME-14	2011/07/11	14:39	12.1	14:54	12.8	15:09	13.4	15:24	14.1	15:39	14.8	15:54	15.6
CME-15	2011/10/29	00:24	13.2	00:39	13.8	00:54	14.3	01:24	15.6	01:39	16.3	01:54	16.9
												02:24	18.2

A.2 3D Reconstruction and Identification of an Event Predicted to Narrowly Miss the Earth

Figure 23: Determination of the EAR value for event UC1-CME-7. A Sun-Earth connection line (blue) is drawn into the 3D GCS model plot and is adjusted in length so that it exactly meets the front of the GCS model. For this event, the connection line does not intersect the GCS front, but just passes it. Thus, the value determined for the EAR is $h_{\text{earth}}/h_{\text{apex}} = 0$, and the event is identified as one that narrowly misses the Earth. The apex height (red) set to a height of 1 AU is also shown.

Acknowledgements

First of all, I would like to express my heartfelt thanks to Dr. Volker Bothmer for coming up with the idea for this work and providing the opportunity to carry it out, as well as for the excellent supervision throughout this project. Special thanks go to Prof. Dr. Ansgar Reiners for agreeing to be the second referee for this thesis.

For reviewing my thesis and providing helpful feedback, I gratefully acknowledge the efforts of Dr. Iulia Chifu, Theresa Reisch, Ole Merkes and Dorian Feisel.

I would also like to express my sincere gratitude to my parents and siblings, from whose faith in me I could always draw motivation during this process.

I would like to thank my physics teacher Dr. Kerstin Reinecke for awakening my interest in physics and nurturing it over years of schooling.

Eigenständigkeitserklärung

“Ich versichere, dass ich die Arbeit selbständig und ohne Benutzung anderer als der angegebenen Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe. Alle Stellen, die wörtlich oder sinngemäß aus Veröffentlichungen oder anderen Quellen entnommen sind, sind als solche kenntlich gemacht. Die schriftliche und die elektronische Form der Arbeit stimmen überein. Ich stimme der Überprüfung der Arbeit durch eine Plagiatssoftware zu.”

Ort, Datum

Unterschrift